

2010 CEDA User Survey Report – Benefits of the CEDA data centres

Graham Parton, Centre for Environmental Data Archival

graham.parton@stfc.ac.uk

Executive Summary

In January 2010 the Centre for Environmental Data Archival (CEDA) 's user communities of the NERC Earth Observation and British Atmospheric data centres (NEODC and BADC respectively) were surveyed as part of a joint RIN-JISC survey examining the "Benefits of research data centres". The results indicate there are little difference between the BADC and NEODC user communities and that overall CEDA is highly regarded in the way it supports research through financial and time efficiencies in data acquisition for research. These results will form part of the larger RIN-JISC study in due course, but also provide a useful evidence base for CEDA to ensure future data archive provision continues to meet the requirements of the research community.

Introduction

The Centre for Environmental Data Archival (CEDA) is based at the Science and Technology Research Council's Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (STFC RAL), Oxfordshire. Its principal mission is to ensure the long term curation of key environmental datasets for use by the atmospheric, environment change and earth observation communities. The majority of these activities are carried out under a Service Level Agreement between STFC and the Natural Environment Research Council (NERC) under which CEDA provides the NERC Earth Observation and British Atmospheric Data Centres (NEODC and BADC respectively). CEDA also provides further archival services, such as the IPCC-Data Distribution Centre and support work for the UK Climate Impact Project, and is involved with development of environmental data archiving standards such as the Climate and Forecasting conventions and metadata modelling involved with the EU Inspire directive .

In 2009 a joint study, entitled "Benefits of research data centres", was commissioned between the Research Infrastructure Network (RIN) and the Joint Information Systems Committee (JISC) to :

"demonstrate the importance, relevance and benefits of effective sharing and curation of research data for the UK research community"

and to

"gather evidence on the extent data centres have been useful to the research community."

Such evidence was gathered through a variety of methods, including a focused examination of a number of data centres from various research fields, taking the form of user surveys. The BADC was identified as one of these data centre to be included in this stage of the RIN-JISC study and CEDA staff were approached in December 2009 to help arrange for the user survey to take place.

While the RIN-JISC user surveys for each data centre had to be kept broadly inline with each other to allow comparisons to be made CEDA staff were able to negotiate suitable adaptations of the user surveys to permit:

- 1) The inclusion of NEODC users within the scope of the survey - although these were not used by the RIN-JISC study this provided a useful opportunity to capture this user community of CEDA services.
- 2) Suitable user survey demographic information to delineate results by research discipline, data centre and institution type. The original categories were altered to match those used in 2007 BADC User Survey to enable comparisons with the previous study to be made.
- 3) Delineation of users of just the BADC and NEODC data centres from one another and from those who use both data centres.

Approach

The RIN-JISC survey was run by the Technopolis Group (<http://www.technopolis-group.com/>) who used Survey Monkey for the survey itself. Following previous experience with the 2007 User Survey for ensuring successful uptake of the survey the research communities of the BADC and NEODC were informed through emails and news item postings before and during the surveying period. Response was excellent, exceeding expectations with 817 respondents in total. As with the 2007 survey, while the 2010 Rin-JISC survey was open from 8th – 29th January peaks in completion of the survey occurred after each email or news item posting, with a constant lower completion rate seen between such reminders. However, unlike the 2007 user survey no incentive was offered to users to complete the survey.

Throughout this report the core user community will be defined as those studying atmospheric chemistry, atmospheric physics, climate change, earth observation and earth science.

Representativeness

Around 80% of respondents are registered users with CEDA allowing the representativeness of the survey results to be established through comparison with the research disciplines, location and establishment type of the survey respondents and user data base.

Examining the research areas of the 2010 survey sample indicates there is a slightly stronger weighting of the core user community for the BADC and NEODC than the CEDA user data base contains. However, when just BADC users are compared to the response of the 2007 survey we see that the split by research area is comparable. In the 2007 survey sufficient demographics were collected to conclude that the 2007 survey was a statistically sound subset of the user community.

2010 - All Respondants

2010 BADC Users

Although the 2010 survey did not capture the location of respondents institute names for the

2007 Survey

2010 User Database

respondents were requested. Taking a conservative estimate from this information roughly 51% are identifiable as being UK based, which is less than would be otherwise expected from the user data base where 61% would be UK based.

The survey sample is further shown to be representative when the organisation type of the respondents (66% academic and 20 % government based) is compared against the user database (72% academic and 17% government based).

The above indicates that there are similarities between the respondent demographics and the user data base. With comparisons between survey demographics and the user data base demonstrated in the 2007 survey, and that there have been no large shifts in BADC and NEODC user communities within the intervening period, it follows that the 2010 survey respondents are a representative subset of the CEDA user community and thus the following conclusions can be taken as indicative of the experiences of the present CEDA user community.

Results

The 2010 survey can be split into a number of sections covering different aspects of the data centres. These are now discussed below. Results are given for the whole of the sample where this is representative of the results when looking at BADC and NEOD C user groups individually. Where there are differences to note these are given.

818 responses were received of which 634 were just BADC users, 58 NEOD users and 126 used both data centres – i.e. 93% of respondents are BADC users (77.5% are just BADC users) while 23% are NEODC users (7% are just NEODC). This compares very well with active CEDA users (those registered for one or more datasets) which give 93% of active users being registered for BADC datasets, while 9 % are NEODC registered users (these figures do not show any cross over users who registered at one data centre but use data in the other.

Data centre usage and Discovery

The appendix shows details of user response to a question on how they discovered the BADC/NEODC. Overall this open text answer indicated that most users came across the data they needed (and therefore the data centre) through recommendation by colleagues, web searches (of which Google was the only search engine specifically mentioned) and through work or study related activity. Linked to work/study activity was the encouraging sign that references to the data centres in academic papers,

Download frequency

conference presentations and meetings also helped to gain exposure for the data holdings and discovery by a wider audience, while a sizable number of users also indicated that they have always know of the BADC and NEODC existence or couldn't recall how they came across relevant data.

Four questions were focused on data centre usage by the respondents. Over all most respondents have been using the facilities for around 3-4 years, likely to be linked to the academic user community where PhDs and post docs have a typical 3 year period. During this period there is a wide spread in the frequency of downloading data – from a small number using CEDA facilities on a daily or weekly basis (7% in total), most on a monthly or annual basis (56%) and around 17% only having downloaded once. The NEODC community tends to download on a slightly more frequent basis.

Respondents showed a fairly even split when asked if their usage had decrease, increased, stayed the same or fluctuated over time, with the smallest group reporting an increase over time (around 12%), while 25% indicated a decrease.

Data Usage

The predominant type of data used by users of the CEDA archives was observational data. Simulated data was used by around 15% of BADC users, but dropped to around 10% for NEODC users, reflecting the relative holdings of the two data centres (NEODC data are earth observation data, while BADC will contain NWP as well as observational data).

There was little difference between the two user communities when the reason for their data use is examined. The primary use is for analysing existing events, where combining with other data also has a significant role. The majority of the “other” uses were for assimilation into model runs and initialising model runs.

Results Reporting and data citation

Unsurprisingly, given the user community is mainly academic, the main research outputs are academic papers, while those listed as “other” were mostly PhD and MSc theses. This is reflected when the target audience for the research outputs is examined where fellow academics are the main target audience for the output.

The questionnaire took the opportunity to poll the respondents for known instances where the data or services from BADC or NEODC have had a notable wider impact. While most responses (see appendix) indicate that the impact was within the published literature, there were a number of references to international (e.g. EU, WMO, IPCC), national (e.g. DEFRA) and agency policy impact.

Respondents were then asked if they cite the datasets and the data providers/creators. It is encouraging that 89% cite the data at least sometimes and only 17% never cited the data provider/creators. In both cases around 60% of respondents stated that they always cited in their research outputs. The main reasons given for users not citing the data set and/or the data creators fell mainly in to three categories: the research had not yet been published; there was confusion between who to cite between the data providers and the data centre (the source of the data used) – often the data centre was cited in some form; that the data creator details were not available; the author list was too long to make citation practical (see appendix for all the text responses)

Impact + Value Added

The 2010 survey had a large section examining the impact that the CEDA data centres have had on the research and outcomes of the respondents. Overall the data available from the CEDA data centres were rated to be at least quite important to the work of over 92% of users, and essential to nearly a quarter of all respondents.

When asked what would have been the impact of not having the data available through the CEDA data centres over half of respondents indicated

that they could have obtained the data elsewhere, but with greater difficulty, while over a quarter indicated that this would be at a greater expense. However, 20 % indicated that alternative data would have had to have been used and a further 18% indicated that no suitable alternative would have been available.

Users were then asked to indicate their level of agreement to a number of questions to assess various impacts that CEDA data centres have had on the respondents' work. These are summarised in the chart below, with the questioned listed afterwards:

- 1 - It has enabled research to go ahead that otherwise might not have done
- 2 - It has permitted more novel research questions to be answered / tackled
- 3 - It has enabled new types of research to be carried out
- 4 - It has reduced the financial cost of data acquisition / processing
- 5 - It has reduced the time required for data acquisition / processing
- 6 - It has reduced duplication of effort (i.e. unnecessary recreation of data)
- 7 - It has improved the efficiency of research
- 8 - It has enabled me to undertake a greater quantity of research
- 9 - It has helped to improve the quality of my research outputs
- 10 - It has improved the evidence base of my research

11 - It has created new intellectual opportunities (e.g. merging of several data sets to answer new questions)

12 - It has increased the use of data in my research

13 - It has improved the quality of the data I use within my research

Immediately obvious from the above results is that the BADC and NEODC are providing a high quality service to the end user community, supporting research in a variety of ways, with the key impacts being the reduction in financial and time overheads for research through reduction of duplication of effort and overall efficiency. A later question in the survey asked if users had to pay to access data while 93% answered no, surprisingly there 4% (24 respondents) who said that they did some or all of the time. There are no charging mechanisms for data access through the BADC or NEODC making this a curious result; one explanation for which could be that respondents were attributing data archive services charged to NERC grants as a “cost” to access data, rather than paying for the archiving services for the data to be supplied to the BADC/NEODC. Unfortunately there was no scope in the survey design to ascertain the reasons for people’s response to this question.

The smallest impact (although over 75% still report an impact to some degree) are the use of data leading to new types of research either directly from a dataset or through new synergies between existing data. This may be in part explained as the data archived at within CEDA may, at times, only be submitted once the new, novel research has taken place, while there is also not as strong an emphasis on research being focused on new synergies of existing data. While this may sound like a deficiency in how the archives support scientific enquiry, if taken just on their own, without comparison to the other areas of greater impact, then it would still easily be shown that the CEDA data centre have a substantial positive impact on the science taking place.

Comparing the results for the two data centres to one another (not shown here) indicated that the NEODC received slightly higher ratings for improving efficiency of research and reducing financial

Has BADC/NEOD improved the culture of data sharing and re-use?

and time overheads for research. The NEODC community also indicated a slightly higher impact on producing new opportunities and increasing the use of data in research.

The overall positive impact of the BADC and NEODC is also reflected in the community’s impression on how BADC and NEODC have improved the culture of data sharing and re-use. 68% of all respondents indicated that the impact had been to a large extent and a further 30% agreed that there was some degree of improvement.

When asked about the impact the lack of existence of the BADC and NEODC respondents generally indicated that research would be severely hampered. While some research would not have taken place others would have found it to be far more time consuming to locate data, if it were possible to source elsewhere. Additional costs for obtaining data was also indicated as a likely outcome, while data quality and confidence in the data were also highlighted as major concerns. In particular the international impact of the BADC and NEODC was noted by a number of users, either directly through CEDA involvement with wider projects or as support for involvement in international projects. Finally, the volume of research work that wouldn't have taken place appears to be quite considerable, while the role of the CEDA data centres in being the archive for projects has also been testified to. All responses are given in the appendix, where a few have been highlighted for interest – including the few negative comments.

Many of the positive comments (e.g. great 1-stop shop for data) were re-iterated when respondents were asked to provide further explanation to their thoughts on the benefits of the BADC and NEODC – all answers are in the appendix.

Satisfaction

Respondents were then asked a series of questions to establish their level of satisfaction with CEDA services and data provision. The 10 questions were:

How satisfied are you with the following aspects relating to BADC/NEODC?

- 1 - The relevance of the data held
- 2 - The comprehensiveness of data held
- 3 - The quality of the data held
- 4 - The ease of navigation (i.e. being able to identify/find relevant datasets)
- 5 - The ease with which you can access / obtain data
- 6 - The quality of the curation of the data (e.g. metadata)
- 7 - The support / help provided (e.g. guidance / helpdesk)
- 8 - The cost of obtaining data
- 9 - The extent to which data holdings are kept up to date / updated regularly
- 10 - The extent to which you are kept informed of developments / additions / changes to data holdings

The results are given below, where the 11th row is an average for all the situations examined.

It is encouraging to see that over all CEDA appears to be meeting the requirements and expectations of the user community, with very small numbers being dissatisfied to any degree, the worst scores coming from the ease of navigating and downloading data – areas that are constantly being improved within CEDA where possible. Again the cost (i.e. lack of it in the case of CEDA) implications for users scored highly, with the user support and helpdesk services also coming out well, reflecting the importance that CEDA places on providing a dedicated, user focused approach to its documentation, help pages and helpdesk services.

For nearly all the questions asked NEODC respondents give slightly higher scorings over all, but with less spread (i.e. typically centred more on satisfied). The only exception to this was that all respondents, regardless of which data centre they used, reported the around 55% being satisfied and 30% very satisfied with the quality of the data available. (This agrees with anecdotal evidence from conversations held and a recent telephone survey carried out by NERC where NERC data products appear to be held in high regard due to their quality).

Respondents were given the opportunity to expand on any very satisfied or very dissatisfied selections that they made. The responses were mixed; on the positive side a large number stated that free access to data was a great thing to have and that the helpdesk/user support was timely and of a high quality and often solving problems/questions. There were mixed feelings about navigation with some praising the ease of navigation and the fact that the data were all in one location, while others lamented the confusing layout and responsiveness. Complaints included lack of sufficient metadata, questioning why access was restricted to data, lack of notification of updates or replacements to datasets and various comments about the MIDAS dataset set (mainly centred

around the data content, lack of coverage and difficulties located suitable data). All responses are given in the appendix.

Access problems described by users (see responses in appendix) centred mainly on the reliability of the Data Extractor service and the limitation placed on that service (imposed to prevent overly large extraction submissions bringing the service down). The limitations of the MIDAS dataset were also emphasised as being a recurring problems for users – either through the structure of the dataset and metadata making it hard to establish/subset data appropriately on just stations returning required data or the need to post-process the data once obtained (either from the files in the archive or from the Data Extractor). These issues are being addressed by CEDA with a WPS to replace the Data Extractor and examination of a useful addition to the Met Office MIDAS system which permits querying of MIDAS stations to help focus on stations likely to return required results. Additional alterations to the MIDAS dataset delivery and ingest have also been examined to address other issues within the dataset.

Improvement Priorities

A number of potential areas for improvement were offered to the respondents to gauge the user community's perspective on these. Of these improving the extent to which processed data are available was indicated as having the highest importance, although this was not much ahead of most other improvements. The only real exception was that improving the terms and conditions of use had a greater number of people rating this as either low or of medium importance. This probably reflects that the datasets are either open access or covered by access agreements which are aimed towards the academic community.

Again the NEODC user community's response was weighted slightly differently to that of the BADC community, with more of higher importance given to all areas, but again not always showing a spread over all the possible answers as seen in the BADC community's responses.

How would you prioritise the following possible improvements to BADC/NEODC?

- 1 - Acquire greater quantities of the same data
- 2 - Acquire different types of data
- 3 - Acquire data available on different topics
- 4 - Improve the quality of the data held
- 5 - Improve the quality of metadata
- 6 - Improve the navigability / guidance
- 7 - Increase the extent to which processed data are available
- 8 - Improve the terms and conditions of use

Respondents were also given the opportunity to convey areas that BADC/NEODC should look to improve (see full answers in appendix). Again improvements to exploitation of the data were mentioned by users, especially related to large datasets and the MIDAS dataset in particular. While example plots and additional metadata to help users ascertain the existence and applicability of a given dataset/parameter were also requested. A desire for improved coverage of certain types of data were also requested – most notably those supporting the renewable energy section (solar irradiance, wind speeds) – as was interoperability between datasets.

Depositing data

Unlike previous BADC surveys the 2010 survey enquired about the end results of respondents' work and depositing of products back at recognised data centres such as the BADC and NEODC. While this was not a comprehensive survey of depositors of data, this does provide a new insight into the user community that has not previously been surveyed before.

Although the NEODC respondents were slightly more likely to produce "value-added" data products, overall only around 15% indicated that they produce such products. Only 7 % of respondents submitted such value-added data products to data centres (5% said to BADC or NEODC, with the remaining 2% indicating that products are archived elsewhere), with a slightly higher number (11% and 6% for NEODC/BADC and other repositories respectively) reporting from the NEODC respondents. This slight shift in the earth observation user community may reflect the numbers of scientists working on producing subsequent higher level products from satellite data held in the NEODC archive or undertaking calibration or validation work.

However, 42% of respondents indicated that they produce new data themselves that may be of interest or use for others. Perhaps of concern for future investigation is that of those that indicated that they produce data of use by others only around half of these archived their data with a data centre (28% said this was with the BADC or NEODC). This could be attributed to lack of funding to support such activities as nearly three quarters of respondents indicated that they could not access

funding for providing data to data centres. A list of responses given when asking for further details of these value added products is given in the appendix.

Final Remarks

The final open question of the survey (see appendix) provided respondents a opportunity to add any additional remarks. These mostly re-iterated comments previously given, but overall emphasised the support for the work of CEDA and the esteem by which the research community holds the data centres and the value of the data holdings. The main negative comment was the restrictions that are in place for some data, but this is a wider policy concern than the main thrust of this survey which was to ascertain the value of the data centres. On this last point, the emphasis on the data access rather than data curation aspects of the data centres was raised by a number of respondents and indicates that this aspect warrants future study.

Conclusion and Further thoughts

The above results indicate that the BADC and NEODC are rated highly by their respective research communities, providing data access and associated services that support research efforts in a variety of manners. Of key importance to the research communities is that CEDA has greatly assisted in making research more efficient by reducing the financial and time overheads for data archiving and accessing.

Compared with the BADC 2007 survey it is encouraging to see that the BADC continues to provide a high quality service, while the inclusion of the NEODC for the first time in a survey helps to provide insights into that particular user community. Overall we see that there are many similarities between the BADC and NEODC user communities, despite the slight differences in target user communities and data needs (BADC has many more datasets supporting, for some data in particular, a very diverse research community, but NEODC datasets tend to be much larger and used by a more specialised community). The similarity between the two communities confirms the strategy within CEDA to approach the management of both data centres in much the same way, which permits an efficient approach within CEDA to its environmental data archival practices.

Although data depositing was briefly touched upon by this survey for the first time further survey work would be recommended to ascertain the skills base that data providers have as well as issues such as funding, delivery issues and onward support. In addition, more work could be carried out to examine the whole data management lifecycle within NERC funded projects to ensure that all aspects are correctly joined up and adequately provisioned. This should take in the initial scoping and costing mechanisms for data management plans at the grant application and subsequent award stage, the communication between NERC project participants and data centres to ensure timely delivery of data products and matters with regards to data access conditions, supply of metadata and use of recognised data and metadata standards and formats. These last two issues are particularly pertinent in light of the EU INSPIRE directive and the need to assist in greater exploitation for ever growing datasets where initial visualisation and/or processing of data at the data centre are essential before subsequent downloading due to bandwidth and storage limits. It

CEDA Users' Institutions and positions.

The following tag clouds have been generated from the list of institutions that users indicated they were involved with and their positions, indicating that they are mainly UK university and NERC and Met Office based users:

Discovery of data/data centres.

Analysis of the open text response permits most responses to be grouped into the following categories:

- Always know/can't recall
- Colleague
- Google
- Meeting/conference
- Notice/publicity
- Publication article/reference
- Redirected from another site/institution
- Web search
- Through work/study
- other answer

The unclassified answers did not show how the data centres were discovered, but are given below, sometimes indicating that users thought this was asking for a reason why they discovered the data, others that didn't fit easily into the above main categories or where the question was not understood (e.g. some complement) :

- AS a source of data for consultancy projects
- BADC store data I need for my research (e.g. ERA-40)
- Connection of stratospheric planetary waves to ionospheric planetary wave type oscillations

Data archiving
Downloaded the XConv software
found the allege to BADC data in one's case study
I like it
I saw the Chulbolton Dish every day when I was flying helicopters at Middle Wallop
I want to use the data
I was aware of the problems of research access to archives via a real time operational
organisation decades ago, before BADC existed
in order to get Hadley SST analysis
IPCC
IPCC data
it has the data I need
It was excellent
Mark New
NERC Atmospheric Sciences Listserv
NERC requirement to submit data to it
Stratosphere is the subject of my investigation
The necessity of global high temporal resolution data
They emailed me asking me to complete this survey
To access global temperature data
To find Central England temperature record
VERY GOOD
Very usefule dataset
We need to use the UKMO/ECMWF data from BADC
When the UK climate data migrated to BADC as part of the UKCIP programme, but I've known of
BADC for a long time--local scene in Oxford

Why users do not cite the dataset or data creator

As I have not yet had any published research

As I said, I still have yet to write any papers that use this data, but will cite both the centre and the creator when I do.

As said before, I had thought a particular data set would be available from BADC, but soon realised that, for some unclear reason, the data announced in a conference as available to the community at large, were still in restricted access.

Assumed citing the data set and centre was sufficient.

Attenuated use due to computer failure

BADC is a holding pen of data and produces no scientific input to reasearch. If we did this , then Bill gates would also require citing.

BADC is the only source for the HadISST data. If you are using it, it had to come from BADC.

BADC supply data to me rather than the data collector

Because Conferences are public.BADC help me to find important Conference meeting for my web site.

Because I did not used the BADC data for formal outputs in the end, oterwise I would acknowledge or cite as per common usage

because Im not find the data which I want

Because so far I have not made use of the data. When I do it (and if I do it) I will definitely acknowledge the concerned institutions/groups/people.

Because the data were never published. The data were just used for an instrument intercomparison and results were never made reported.

because where the data is stored is not relevant to the scientific integrity but where and how it was produced is.

Because, using those data, I haven't publish any work in the international journal.
Citing the data source seemed more appropriate than the data creator..
Data Centre/Data Set: I specify that I am using the NERC MST radar, and the format of the data, I have not felt it necessary to discuss it's availability. Creation/gathering: The data used is from specific campaign periods for which I am the campaign co-ordinator.
Data creator has sometimes changed over time (when using several datasets) and/or not relevant
Data has not been "used", but have username as access was required to BADC systems during UKCP09 development and deployment
Data is cited as specified on the BADC site; the data creator/gatherer is not indicated.
Data not used in published material, only for my reference.
data were taken for internal comparisons or not used in peer reviewed publications
Did not include BADC data in my final thesis, so no need to cite.
Didn't realise it was required
don't know
don't know the data creator
Don't know the originator
ESA Cat-1 project usage
ESA deny me access to rain data for ph.D research in comparison with TRMM satellite product
For the aerial images it will depend on the type of output in what detail the origin/original purpose of the data is mentioned.
Forgot
Haven't answered Q16 - I am part of the organisation creating the data (ARSF), NEODC just holds our data. If I obtained non-ARSF data from NEODC and used it in a publication I would certainly cite NEODC and probably the data creator.
Haven't obtained any data from BADC
Havent written a paper where I have used the whole timeseries of data I use yet. But the data was measured by someone that i have to quote. Could quote BADC if you would prefer
haven't yet accessed the data set
How impirical/quantifiable is your data? I would LOVE to expand your data - with others. I am waiting for the political motivation (shift) to align the data with others. It may never happen - but I'm waiting....
I am following the international practice,the data creator is mostly not mentioned
I am not aware of the Data creators in question
I can't check every paper ... but we do acknowledge both every time (BADC, MetOffice) in some form every time.
I can't download dataset from BADC/NEODC
I cite the data creator always then I aknowledge the Data centre
I cite the original source of the data but not the data centre. The reason is probably to keep things relatively concise
I decided not to use BADC data.
I do not know the data creator.
I don't know that I've ever had this information as part of the data set but I could be mistaken
I dont know who is the data creator.
I don't known yet if these data will be usefull for my study
I don't use any data
I don't write papers
I don't write papers, I just download the data that's required by others in the department.
I follow the guidelines given on the web. But this is written confusing: 1. When using the data set in a paper, the following is the correct citation to use: Rayner, N. A.; ... 2. Citation UK Meteorological Office, Hadley Centre. HadISST 1.1 ...
I give credit to the BADC for data but wasn't aware of the requirement to credit data

creator/gatherer which I am not sure if available on BADC
I have cited the data center which makes the facility to put data for me.
I have just downloaded this January, and am on the way to report my research. So, after completing analysis, I will cite the data stuff.
I have never downloaded data.
I have not noticed the information to cite.
I have not published analyses with these data yet
I have not yet formally published the research using CET (but have given presentations in-house) but I will always follow the accepted norms for citation in the field.
I have not yet used it in a published paper. I will / would cite if this changed.
I have yet to make any formal publications using BADC data.
I haven't published anything yet
I haven't made any formal outputs yet.
I haven't publish any paper or report yet so no need to cite DATA centre or data creator. I am at the beginning of data analysis.
I haven't written a report / article yet in which I used the data.
i never thought it was necessary
I was not aware that the data creator/gatherer needed to be cited. I have always referenced either the Met Office or the Hadley Centre in my publications.
I will cite the data centre from which it is most easily obtained - that in many cases would NOT be the BADC. Each data set should be tagged with the formal citation and ideally a DOI or similar electronic unique identifier; see <http://www.pangaea.de/>
I would acknowledge BADC rather than cite the dataset, often I'm combing BADC data with others anyway.
I would always acknowledge BADC. I hope also to acknowledge, e.g. ECMWF, if using trajectory service, or Met Office, for MIDAS data, but couldn't swear that I had always included these "data gatherers" as well.
If Chinese could be used in the explorer, we would feel very happy
If there is a long gap between acquisition and write-up I forget to do so, for which I apologise, because that is not acceptable.
I'm not associated with any interested person or organization
I'm not sure what you mean by the 'data creator'. I cite BADC and MIDAS.
In relation to weather data, I don't know who should be cited as the creator
In the end the data did not play a substantial role in the results.
individuals not credited by BADC?
Initially i have requested radiosonde data for my academic research, however access has not been granted
It is generally observational Met data that I use and this either has many data gatherers such as rainfall data or the names are not available on the site
It never occurred to me to do so.
It was used during pre-flight briefings within a small group of people where the data source was quite obvious.
I've only used BADC to download the UM so the above questions are not really relevant.
Mainly because the name of the data creator/gatherer is not generally know - only the name of the organisation responsible.
metoffice is the data owner as far as I understand
My project never reached the publication stage.
N/A - haven't published papers using BADC data
Never occurred to me to do so
No
No data downloaded and used from NEDDC

No date we have not published a paper using BADC-accessed data as far as I am aware. In the near future we likely will do and will of course cite the data centre/creator.

no formal output as yet

no idea who the data creator/gatherer is for the datasets i use

No other reason except that all the previous citations refer only to the data centre

No reason other than citing BADC seems sufficient

Normally not cited in the references but in either the text or the acknowledgements

Not generated published work from using the data yet (when the time comes, there will be a full citation).

Not published

not published as research papers

Not really applicable (too many of them)

Not Referenced yet for even internal studies.

Not relevant to trajectories?

Not sure who the data creator is. I cite the data the way I am requested on your server. If the data creator as well as the data centre is cited in this text then I cite the creator as well. I've not looked in a while.

Not used in formal publications, but would cite appropriately when used.

Not used the data accessed. If publicising in any way, I would reference the data correctly.

Not yet published

One use only, informal internal report only, not for outside consumption.

only tests e.g. download, compare data with other,...

only used it once

Publication not yet complete.

research in progress, as yet unpublished

Results given to UK university. They would have provided citation in their reports.

Sometimes it is not clear who data creator was. I thinking citing BADC (or BODC for example which I use more) is enough.

SPARC-IPY, always site BADC CCMVal data - not always site BADC

Summary data attributed to organization. Database I don't believe mentions who scribbled down the weather observations ;)...

The authors of any papers are expected to cite BADC and/or the data creator/gatherer, is indicated by the terms set by BADC when the data was downloaded.

The Data Centre is a facility for which we pay a fee (though our grants), they do not have an academic input into the work and there don't need to be cited. It is also not obvious how we cite a data store

The data was part of another subgroup of data.

The data were from a collaborative project we were part of; it was therefore appropriate to cite the data producer, but the means of sharing the data was a technicality as far as I was concerned.

The GASSIM modelling data is rarely looked at the models resulatant grapghs however everyone looks at and software does not provide option to include sources

The need has not arisen yet/no publications yet.

The work isn't finished

There is no data creator/gatherer name to cite since the data usually comes from the daily routine radiosonde flights from airports over a long period of time.

There were too many creators for the CET record

We cite the UK Met Office, and anyone who seeks to obtain that data would find that it was obtained from the BADC. The Met Office produced the data, is responsible for its quality, and controls its distribution.

whichever citation is recommended in the dataset description

Please briefly explain any other implications for you / your research if BADC/NEODC did not exist

A number of quotations have been highlighted below to indicate the range of impacts, including the few negative responses. However, there are cases where the respondent has deviated away from the question in hand and so replies should also be read in a more general context about BADC and NEODC services and facilities.

A sole point of access for the data is essential to carry out final checking and to verify which stations are still active.

A third-party provider such as NCAR acts as another layer between the data producer and user. It would be better to obtain BADC data directly from source (in the event that information about the data ever needs to be transmitted).

About a third of my research publications over the last 10 years would have been impossible without BADC

Access to (A)ATSR archives would be harder. I am also involved in creating data in the form of the GRAPE archive on the BADC. Would need to find an alternative storage for the dataset if this had not been available.

Access to datasets would require liaison with and possible payment to the primary data holders, such as the Met Office. This is likely to be time consuming and unlikely to stimulate further interest in comparing biological data with climate records (my main use of BADC).

Access to such data would be a concern. the data I would have access to would not be of the same quality (specifically in terms of spatial and temporal resolution)

Access to the UKMO datasets would be difficult and our work would suffer accordingly.

Accessing data would be a drain on my time and limited resources. Also data from other sources may not be of the same quality and could effect my analysis.

Accessing the data necessary for my research through the EUMETSAT UMARF online ordering system is extremely laborious, and doesn't allow ftp access for obtaining multiple files.

Accessing weather data for some locations would not be possible

Added costs for data archival, dissemination and support staff time would have to be included on subsequent grant applications. **Could not guarantee long term stewardship of the data.**

All of the choices in Q19 would apply in different cases. BADC provides a convenient one-stop shop for acquiring daily rainfall data series. In some cases, the data could be acquired elsewhere but that would be time-consuming; in other cases, it would be very difficult if not impossible to get hold of the data.

Also see other interesting data sets while browsing my own - **outreach and education role of BADC/NEODC is important**

Although I did not use or access data as they were not available at that time...the data would have been useful to my graduate thesis had it been available.

An important source of data. I guess some of the data would not become available otherwise.

as an unsupported researcher this resource is very valuable

BADC data can not be validated at ground stations in Africa

BADC is a "one-stop" shop for relevant data. Very convenient archive/repository. Doubtful if I would have the time or effort to find the equivalent resources elsewhere.

BADC is a 'one stop' shop for accessing climatic data and keeping in touch with new developments.

BADC is central to easy access to data which is at the heart of science and reproducibility of research. It just has to be there.

BADC is really quite since it collects a lot of different data sets. Further, it is quite is to downlaod the data which I really appreciate.

BADC is very important. Without BADC, the research data would be stored somewhere and would not as convinient as now.

BADC largely facilitates the collection of data

BADC made the HadISST data easily and conveniently accessible. I am looking forward to accessing other BADC datasets in the near future.

BADC makes access to data easier, but it is still often easier to access met analyses etc through USA sites.

BADC supply the Met Office archive data: there is no substitute for these data. Loss of access would prevent climatic factors being assessed in any longitudinal study.

Badly inconvenienced on an irregular and unpredictable manner
campus weather station
Cannot be replaced
cannot get the study going

Certain avenues of research would be closed due to unattainable data - either due to availability or cost limitations.

Certain datasets at BADC are easily available elsewhere, but other datasets are not and it would be difficult to replace them or find alternative data.

C'mon - we presently NEED data-based info to make up projections. If they are scientific and recognised - we need them! But LESS of the justifications (unless YOU are under pressures to justify existence...)

combined some data published

Correlations of variables to SST would be very much more difficult
could not apply my simulations over UK

CRU

Currently none but is always useful to have access to more than one dataset

DAAC

Data delivery is an important function and should be funded. If not through BADC, the Hadley Centre would have to serve the data.

Data would be more difficult to find; there is also the question of quality control and documentation

Days, letters, and months wasted trying to get something close to what you need

difficult to explain

Difficult to gauge the impact of storm surges (which i was looking at) without rainfall data. Research would lack all significant variables.

Difficulty for research

Environment Agency or Met.Office could provide some of observed data.

Essential to my research

Even if I did not use BADC data in the end, BADC was very useful to source data and get an understanding of what was available; I could find a suitable alternative from my organisation database because I knew what to look for after consulting and retrieving data, and its metadata, from BADC.

Extra costs to the public purse, outside the academic community

extra time spend in looking for compilations

Field campaign data would have had to be stored elsewhere, which would have made it more difficult to access, and the data would probably not all be in the same place.

find others

Finding data will be much more difficult

Focus on similar data from other countries

Getting hold of the data I use on a day to day basis would be hugely more complicated, difficult, time consuming and probably expensive.

Given the nature of our work, which has a more theoretical focus and less reliance on complex datasets, the implications would be minimal. In removing the overly "box ticking" to storing model output from NERC contracts, one might argue that this might be beneficial in saving valuable PDRA time archiving model data for its own sake even when it is unlikely to be of any practical use to other researchers. Of course, a better approach would be to develop a sensible model data archiving policy at NERC.

Global data in convenient format would be missing.

Great accuracy loss

Greater expense and less comprehensive/rigorous analysis

Greater shoe leather costs in finding data sets. Costs in retrieving data. Slower to advance on research activity.

Hard to assess as other sources of data would possibly take its place.

higher costs

How can you describe the physical oceanography of coastal waters and estuaries, and the data collected there, without high quality, frequently measured and available met data - impossible! hyperspectral images would not be as well disseminated so the body of knowledge would not be building as quickly

I am eager to use it rigorously from this year.

I am obviously biased, but I cannot help having the feeling that BADC/NEODC is a bit too much geared towards the UK university research community.

I am sure I would have obtained the data, though I really don't know whether it would have been more or less difficult to access.

I assume the historic met data would be held elsewhere on the internet - I can not predict if this would take me more or less time to locate and collect. I suspect that charges would apply.

I cooperate with staff at BADC over use and application of the data. This could be brought to an end if BADC didn't exist

I could not do it as far as I know

I could not research the mitigation of Climate Change.

I don't believe there would be any.

I don't know other organization that have this kind of data

I don't know right now

I DON'T WASTE MY TIME

I expect one of the PIs would host the data on one of their websites (this does happen to an extent already)

I feel safe for being able to get reasonable and consistent data at any time I need it and I really found that accessing BADC data is very useful, but for me it is not a friendly interface for searching and looking for the data I need, especially when I was a new user

I guess that I would be involved with data delivery to another data centre.

I have found it very difficult to access met data from elsewhere, the Met Office are not as helpful as BADC and they only allow you limited data sets before charging. As a student with limited funds I have found BADC to be very helpful, which takes the stress out of finding up to date information, which is vital to the success of research.

I have not analyzed the experiment data that were acquired in the NCAVEO Field Experiment at Chilbolton, June 2006. Without these data, my current research will be affected.

I have not used yet

I have to find another data which similar function

I mainly used BADC for the CSIP data, which I could get from the MO, although with much much much more effort

I might spend more time to find the data for my research

I need BADC given that it is an important input of referenced data

I need to find other source to access the data.

I would find it very difficult to complete my research

I rely heavily on a close working relationship with BADC to validate and partner on informatics research.

I selected the country which have the precipitation data for our research. If the UK didn't have the data, I changed the target country.

I should note that I only try to use the BADC SLP data once. I am not updated but BADC provides the access to one of the more comprehensive datasets. All data providers, such as BADC are very important for the research in atmospheric physics.

I think it is important to have access to certain datasets e.g. met data; just like having access to the AURN pollutant data is important. So that you can place your own measurements in a wider environment and conduct comparisons

I will be missing something important, if this data were not available, as it will hamper running UKMO model

I will find other data for substitution.

I will have to find an alternative to get the data needed.

I will lose an important point of information of conferences and meetings

I work with a number of the BADC members on a joint European project and they have world leading expertise which is essential for the UK to maintain.

I work with observations, so you can imagine the consequences if no data available!

I would also have troubles distributing the data which I generate.

I would be in big trouble. The BADC provides a (mostly) convenient way to access many different forms of data, which I use for personal research and for teaching (primarily student projects). It has

been extremely useful for me.

I would be unable to carry out some aspects of my research and would therefore have results with less scientific strength.

I would have less accurate climate data for my models, which already have large errors

I would have substantial difficulties in accessing operational precipitation radar datasets and this would not allow me to validate products from my satellite rainfall estimation algorithms.

I would have to attempt to access data directly from the data gatherer (UK Met Office) who do not have to provide that data, so the same data set may not be available. **The time and cost implication for data collection could affect the research outcomes.**

I would have to create the dataset myself e.g. running RCM simulations

I would have to find the data elsewhere.

I would have to rely on data from the USA (NCALM for free LiDAR data), or purchased datasets (very expensive) for my research.

I would have to spend time finding out where the data was available, then requesting it

I would have to use only the radar data bought from the Met Office by the water company for which I do part of my research. This is a much more limited dataset (in time duration and area).

I would like to access the operational ECMWF data from your site but I am unable to access to it. Since it is required for my research work. Hence, I can see the comparison between UKMO and operational ECMWF. Kindly consider my request and do the needful

I would like to start using CLAU data because of the enhanced resolution over 2xdaily OLR data from NOAA. I've just not gotten the chance to write the code to read it for my analyses. I do value the data despite my answer to 18. I've seen results with it compared to OLR and I believe the results are better for looking at tropical convective variability on synoptic time scales.

I WOULD NEVER HAVE GRADUATED I GUESS-WHERE WOULD I HAVE OBTAINED ALL THAT DATA, ESPECIALLY FOR RAINFALL IN EASTERN, CENTRAL AND SOUTHERN AFRICA?

I would not be able to carry out my research. Weather data is an essential element of my species distribution models

I would not be able to devote necessary time to searching for alternative data sources, as research is entirely undertaken in my own time.

I would not have access to the data set at all I think, as I do not have funding now that I am a Senior Research

I would not have done the research that I did. There are no ongoing implications since I am now working in a different area and am semi-retired.

I would receive fewer unwanted emails from BADC/NEODC

I would spend more time obtaining the data set and less time would be available for my research.

I would spend more time in accessing the data sites as the BADC website is pretty organized and it allows me to access the relevant data sets quicker

I wouldn't be able to "prove" a hypothesis with reasonable confidence.

I'd have to go to the originators and hence would not have a single portal

I'd have to have multiple accounts across the webtubes

I'd have to, for example, use other packages for calculating trajectories. This can be done using a model in the States. I believe this model is good, but I don't know how it compares with BADC. In terms of output, there are pros and cons with both.

I'd rely only on one other data source. Would I use only this other data source my research results wouldn't be independent. However, the overall research goal can still be accomplished.

I'd spend less time navigating your dataset ...

I don't know

If data had to be accessed directly from individual organisations, I would expect this to be much less efficient than accessing through BADC.

If I had to pay for the datasets I use, my research would probably not exist because of the absence of available funds.

If it didn't exist then I'm sure some other mechanism would be created without much difficulty.

If the BADC did not exist it would most likely be more difficult and time consuming to obtain the data.

If the BADC did not exist, some research could not carry out successfully.

If the NEODC did not exist, I would likely not be aware of the existence of many datasets which I have analysed and found useful.

If we cannot get DATA from BADC, it's a pity important but not studied much. try to devote more time to see n use your data.... important method for understanding causal association with vitamin D would not be possible. Impossible to analyse flying locations for high gust risk.

IN THIS INSTENCE THE VALUE OF THE DATA IS WITH REFERENCE TO THE MILLIONS OF PEOPLE IN 18 COUNTRIES IN SUB SAHARAN AFRICA THAT HAVE BEEN AFLICTED BY MAJOR SHIFTS IN THEIR WEATHER PATTERNS SUFFICIENT TO PRODUCE FAMINE, WAR, DEATH ON A BIBLICAT SCALE. ACCESS AND UNDERSTANDING THE DATA ALLOWS FOR STABILITY AND FORWARD PLANNING TO A REGION THAT HAS TILL NOW BEEN CLASSIFIED AS A BASKET CASE..

International collaboration would suffer

initially i have palned to access 10 years radiosonde data for my research.I am going to do pull out the data soon and start my new research project

It could be very hard to me to do simulations of the future climate.

it is bad

It is good to be able to point the reader to electronically available data, whereas they would need to look into some very old journal articles, etc.

It is often true that a research project nowadays required more than one source of data/information. The real value of BADC/NEODC is to be stressed that variety of dataset is easily obtained in one place. It is very dificult.

It is very efficient to use BADC/NEODC since the data can be downloaded from a single site. Without this resource I am not sure how I would be able to source the data that I require to drive hydrological and water quality model applications. This resource is invaluable to me.

It make obtaining the information I need for my research much more time consuming and difficult which would be a very ineffecient use of time

It might encourage a private-public partnership along the lines of Ubuntu instead of privatisation of data sets with strict control. We tried to get our portal to have direct access to BADC so users would not have to bother with sourcing and formatting--they were pretty good at blocking any efforts like this so we turned to other sources.

It seems difficult for such research institutions as CRU to act as data services as well. We need institutions dedicaded to data services.

it will be difficult to get the data with a better documentations

It will be more difficult for me.

It will seriously affect our research activities.

It would add to work load and expense. Other sources may be found but the quality of data would be poorer.

It would be a great inconvenience, as I use these data for analysis and model evaluation it would be a lot more difficult to find the alternative information, and this would take a lot more time.

It is possible that a full alternative option would not be available, but academic papers would all have the same problem so this should not affect my likelihood of being published

It would be a major pain in the neck. For most of my research the relevant data could be obtained from individual institutions but this would be much more time consuming (hence, expensive) and, possibly, less carefully prepared which would force me to spend a great deal more of my time in checking, verification and mucking about with odd file formats.

It would be almost impossible for me to access the same amount of data, and analyses/results would be much the poorer for it

It would be difficult or requires a lot of effort to get data of this kind of diverse and comprehensive in nature

It would be difficult to put context to specific research outcomes

It would be exceptionally difficult to retrieve the data collected without the NEODC database.

It would be extremely time consuming and expensive to source similar data and produce it in a useable format. The comunity would find it difficult to conduct long-term climate change studies without the BADC.

It would be harder to find or get hold of certain UK research data/observational data. Whilst I do not use this data very often, BADC allows an easy method of finding this data.

It would be less accurate

It would be more difficult to find out the operational status of weather stations, and therefore more difficult to advise consultants on which weather stations available for dispersion modelling studies. It is good to have the information in one place, rather than having to go through the Met Office every time.

It would be much more complicated to collate data from different sources.

It would be much more difficult to even know the existence of observational/experimental data set

It would be very bad

It would be very difficult to be updated every time new data become available

It would be very difficult to continue.

It would be very difficult to find long term data from, say, wind power developers with which to create our statistical wind models

It would be very hard to analyze long term trends in ocean conditions, and that situation might affect interpretations of current and future events on the marine fauna

It would be very helpful if more processed data are provided. As all the data on the site have been used by people, there may be possibility that some further processed data can be provided to user to save time and effort, especially for those who are not experts in image processing.

It would become challenging and time consuming to the extent that the research would not be undertaken

It would degrade the quality of some of our monitoring data as the BADC data is used as a reference. Some pieces of work would be a lot harder, time consuming and potentially expensive to complete

It would eliminate a dataset important to many studies comparing meteorological analyses and other combined meteorological/satellite data analysis studies. Would eliminate a derived dataset that is widely used in the atmospheric science (especially stratospheric science) community.

It would have been harder to access the data I needed, although still possible. The support from BADC was v helpful in speeding the process.

It would make data access, collation and usage more time consuming, expensive and thus increase time taken to initiate a data base to facilitate the research interest of the moment.

It would make it more difficult to obtain the necessary meteorological data used in my research.

It would make the data I require much more difficult to access

It would not be available in a central storage, more time to find, etc

It would require going to several places to gather the data, instead of a central repository.

It would simply require much more time, stress and expense to access!

It would take longer to find relevant datasets and possibly have to carry out pre-processing. **BADC saves time and money**

It would take more time to find an alternative source.

It would very probably involve much more time consuming effort to obtain - possibly at a significant cost.

it's also the time and convenience of access that matters

Its important that such archives exist and continue to accumulate data which over time will become increasingly valuable.

It's impossible to know the oceanic and atmospheric condition without long-term time series data reserved from BADC/NEODS

It's really important to have a huge platform that gathers and structure lots of different information/data.

Lack of access would remove the impetus to investigate relationships between public health data and climatic variables

Large overhead in terms of time and direct costs.

Lengthy, time consuming, expensive acquisition of data

Less data analysis

Less distribution of MTCI L3 data produced by Infoterra Ltd.

life would be much more difficult. Data consistency would be a challenge.

Likely to have to maintain local archives to much greater extent.

Locating datasets might prove a lot more difficult

Lower quality research More time spent chasing less user-friendly/comprehensive sources

Main impact would be on time to track down and obtain data from elsewhere; it would probably also mean we were less ambitious in what we attempted in terms of research because of the difficulties of

getting adequate data access.

Make life more difficult!

May not attempt some analyses

models would not be able to use the easy to access historical weather data for hindcasting

More difficult access to data

More difficult access to reliable data

More difficult to obtain data and probably impossible to do certain important modeling studies

More legwork to assemble data, possibly having to pay to access data.

More time consuming and difficult

More time for data search

More time spent trying to obtain data

More time would be required searching for data that may or may not exist. It would be difficult to share data with other researchers.

More time-consuming/costly to acquire meteorological data - impact depends on project requirements and funding

More work

more works

Much less easy to quickly check if actual data supported theory or 'anecdotal' evidence

much more time consuming to gather data

Much more time consuming to obtain the data sets I need.

Much more time would be taken up trying to source relevant data and in checking the accuracy of the datasets

My dissertation would have been impossible to complete.

my publication would not be strong enough to publish

My research work would be not so good

My research would be impossible and many opportunities for maximising the use of data already commected would be lost. This would leading to wasting of valuable research funds by duplication of datasets and a loss of temporal continuity of environmental data at a time where change in our environment is crital to understand. **Data would reside in university departments and lost when departments close and research changes direction.**

My research would be less unique.

My research would be less useful to the international community. It is important to note - funding is extremely difficult to obtain, and there is an ad hoc approach to what has been, and is done by 'authorities' who do not have the suitable field data on which to formulate policy.

My research would not be possible to carry out in the present form

my teaching would be severely affected as students would not be able to pay for the data

My work concerns retrodiction of former precipitation using a variety of proxy data. I use BADC precipitation data sets - often data not held elsewhere - to establish comparisons with the present. This would be much more difficult to achieve if BADC did not exist.

n/a

n/a

NCEP, ECMWF

need more effort to collect data

need to find other data source

NEODC makes life much easier when I am trying to find out what data is available, in particular the new interface for the UK datasets which allows you to navigate to a location to see what is there is great. The aquisition of the NEXTMAP data by NERC was a masterstroke and has enabled me to do things that simply would not have been possible without it. Access to this data through NEODC makes the process of aquiring high resolution elevation data for the UK fast and painless.

NERC ARSF would have to archive our data elsewhere. Since I know that our users access ARSF data from NEODC (we get support queries in relation to data downloaded from NEODC), this would have to be made available in a manner funded from the ARSF budget, which would probably be more difficult to access, possibly would be charged for and would involve additional ARSF staff time to administrate. The likely result of this would be ARSF data being much less widely used by anyone other than the PI requesting the data.

NERC, NCAR

no comment

No data centre

no idea

no meteorological data to calibrate a model

NOAA

none

none

none

None

none

none

none confirmatory data only

None I can think of presently

Not sure how to answer this question

Not too much implicated to me because other data source especially solar data available elsewhere

Obtaining data from multiple sources with application procedures and convoluted access rights is already difficult enough. Without repositories such as BADC/NEODC this would be made even harder as you would have to do your own detective work to find the data you require. There is still so much more that BADC could have on its site; this would make it even better.

Obtaining quality controlled data would be more difficult - probably more effort would be required from me to locate and quality control data.

One of the main benefits of the BADC is the vast collection of datasets which allow an awareness of the many aspects of work going on in multiple fields

Only model investigation and sporadic observational data

papers of lower quality

Part of the research that I do would simply not have been possible and it would have been much more difficult to design/develop suitable research approaches.

Please recommend that where else we can access each data set.

Possibility of looking for different data for different periods at various places, like to think BADC as a data 'supermarket' almost free of charge

potentially data from campaigns would not be collected together so well and obtaining a number of different data sets would involve more time and effort

Probably impossible to do work involving climate data

Probably would not have performed this task nor been asked to. If the data wasn't available at BADC, the question needing answering would have not been asked.

Reduced confidence in exposure-response data related to pollutants and illness/death

Reduced scientific outputs due to time and cost obtaining data elsewhere.

research would be harder

RELIABLE RAINFALL RECORDS FOR USE IN HYDROLOGICAL MODELLING ARE NOT READILY AVAILABLE -- BADC IS THE PRIMARY SOURCE FOR MANY OF MY COLLEAGUES

Research findings would be incomplete and not as full as they should be

Research would not have moved on in the same way

search for other data sources like ESG or other

See above

Slow down of my research

Some data sets would simply not exist (in an accessible) format

Sorry, I hope that BADC/NEODC give me access to the assimilation data anymore!

spatial cover of stations would be worse

Still problems remains because most of the time you need datasets available in BADC but you don't have access like ECMWF or AMMA for which the access is theoretical, but in reality it is so complex and the download time a trap

Storage problems due to the use of high resolution model data

Streamlined data collection would have been a hindrance

studying for BSc

The additional time and cost would be a severe handicap to my research

The analysis (relating marine mammal behaviour to weather) would almost certainly not be possible. The archiving of data would have to be supplied by other means. The legacy of existing data would not be efficiently used.

The BADC is a widely used community resource as a one stop shop of the data required. The same data would be available from the primary gatherers, but this process would be slower, more dependant on individuals responding to requests and a centralised repository encourages better data formatting, manual pages, transparency and usability.

The BADC makes it possible to create large data repositories where a global community of researchers can pool their model results, allowing the community to inter-compare results. The availability of a large, easily accessible data repository allows for a more in-depth analysis of the results that would not be possible if other, more ad hoc, approaches to sharing data were required.

The BADC provides an essential service to allow easy access to the data that is collected as part of projects that I work on

The comparable data that I have found was not quite as easy to analyze, so the BADC data saved me some time.

The cost of data would deter research by individuals with small funding

The data base of the data would not be complete and probably have to wait for sometime to have more data available

The data centers are absolutely essential for research to proceed efficiently.

The data I could find would be much more limited and it would greatly constrain the aims of my research. I do think the BADC/NEODC is of high importance nowadays and hope it keeps on going for the future

The data we sought is also available from the IPCC archives, so the non-existence of BADC would have little impact.

The data were used to compare with other geophysical data. the comparison was of interest but not the main thrust of the paper.

The distribution of the Met Office's data would become a burdensome additional activity by that office.

The doadnloaded Eskdalemuir met data became essential for my PhD research, whitouh which I would have not been able to publish an important paper.

The existance of the facility has greatly enhanced my research and teacing - in terms of expense, speed of access (I can do it from home and the data comes through very quickly) and ease of collection

The expertise, security, and permanence of the BADC is absoltely essential for us to fulfill our role in the NERC/EPSRC/ESRC funded UK Energy Research Centre (UKERC) - where we are making nationally important datasets available to the energy research community.

The implications would be bad. BADC provides a superb service, without which data access would be extremely difficult and time draining.

The loss of time because of more complicated data processing from other sources

The Met Office charges commerical rates for access to data which is well beyond normal research grant allowable costs.

the output of new model Exps, in particaulr high resolution modelling

The project would not have started.

the quality of my gappy weather data would not improve

The region which am working with would be difficult to work with and even hav some papers produced.

The research work may not be full

The results would be much weaker. The temperature data I require validates my results

The simulations/ reanalysis data is quiet difficult to get, which has been supplimented by BADC

The systematic uncertainties to the atmospheric model applied to the telescope simulations would not have been quantified correctly, leading to a consistent and hidden bias being introduced in the observational conclusions.

The time needed to asemble long term rainfall data sets would not be available to me and I would stop this area of research

The time to gather data would be increased.

The variety of data sources would be decreased, which would have implications for the breadth of study, or the generality of implications, that research would have.

there aren't any

there is no other such implications involved yet

There would be no change

There would be no technical support for data access and information on data types etc (metadata). these are essential data of growing importance given current implications for every earth/biological science of climate change

Thinking of things like the Data Extractor, I think it is fabulous I can access Met Data for any number of UK sites for any time period. Considerable effort has clearly gone into making this archive accessible

This is difficult to assess. In general, recognizing the expense of keeping such an organization operating, I believe more sources of this data is better. The data is very important and redundancy seems the proper course to me.

This is the only European data centre of excellence. If this did not exist we will have to rely on American or Chinese sources. This data portal is a must and needs to be enhanced for attracting more users.

This would impact significantly on collaborative projects which are the foundation stone of most major atmospheric/chemistry/climate research today.

Time would be wasted trying to track down data and organise access to restricted datasets. At the moment the service is efficient and the staff helpful

To access GHCN (USA)

To be totally honest, I think it would have very little implication. In some cases, the data would be easier to get elsewhere, and in other cases it would be a little harder but generally I believe I would be able to find all of the data that I need from other sources.

tragic !! could not design any software which are of benefit of trainee and professional aviation pilots UK Met Office and MADIS (<http://madis.noaa.gov/>)

Until data was available from BADC it was only available from the Met Office and at a high cost. It was often difficult to gauge how much data was available and what the quality was.

Use alternative data

Use of datasets is likely to become more important in the future in my field, so ongoing support of data centres is vital

Used as data centre serving data for a project I work on so if it did not exist these resources would need to be found elsewhere or developed within the project.

Using alternative temperature sources but losing precision in our research

Using BADC data associated with rainfall is one of approaches for my research. If there is no available data, I will consider other approaches.

Verification of model results through observational data would not be possible.

Very serious: I depend on NextMap for my spatial analysis in the UK

We archive all our project data in-house and also at BADC when required to do so. The inflexibility of archival at BADC sometimes makes use of the data difficult and so we frequently mine our own archives or directly contact the data providers. Nevertheless, BADC provides a valuable one-stop-shop for the majority of NERC-funded programmes we work with and serves as a useful repository for our work.

We are developing distribution maps for tropical species, without these data our results would be incomplete

We are particularly interested in upper atmosphere winds (we run mesosphere radars). No satellite does a good job measuring wind, and even if one did, the sampling is sparse. We are interested in the polar vortices. If BADC did not exist we would look for other assimilated models - which to my present knowledge would either be hard to access; limited in scope, or we could not afford them. We do have some years of other models (ECMWF, CMAM) with higher time resolution, but this was related to the International Polar Year, not a continuing access.

We will have to conduct more wind probing flights before our main scientific balloon flights to predict the balloon flight path.

we will not have a clue of the condition of that study area

we would have depended on satellite data and have requested some modelers to simulate the conditions with available inputs

We would have had to establish (or find) another data center for our station project.

We would have to archive and distribute our own data ourselves

We would likely be using similar services outside the UK.

We would not win funding for research projects - the data we have used from NEODC have been fundamental to the core aspect of the research project. There may be alternatives but it would take a substantial amount of time to find out if there are and where we could them from.

We would put up instrumentation to measure what we need for the time period of our research. But BADC makes it convenient for us.

We'd have to self-archive data, which would be a considerable effort and probably not done as well.

When running a climate model various data provisions are essential for initialising the model and for result analysis

Without the BADC I would have to manually collate the observations from 339 weather stations in Cumbria that have operated for some period between 1900 and present day. I think this would be a PhD in itself, and would severely reduce the amount of time available for analysis.

Working as an individual without strong academic links in the field the availability of Proudman Lab data was invaluable.

would be hard to coordinate access to datasets

Would cause me to look for other data sets for my students

Would have to buy data access

WOULD HAVE TO HAVE USED NASA OR EX.SOVIET DATA

Would have wasted a lot of time (hence tax-payers money) on searching for the data from other sources. Would have had less confidence in the reliability / validity of the data obtained; although I don't expect BADC to ensure the data is perfect I have confidence that it is what it says it is ...

Would make data gathering much more difficult and prolonged.

Would make my work extremely difficult

Would possibly have to rely on assimilated model data (e.g. from ECMWF) rather than observational data

Would probably never have had a UKCP project to be involved in.

Would waste a lot of my (costly) time. Access to Met Office data etc would be more complex (time-wasting)

Wouldn't be wasting my time trying to obtain info from an organisation that doesn't want to provide it

You have to work with data which are available. If certain data are not available we may not be able to answer specific research questions.

Please provide any further explanation you would like to give as to the benefits of accessing data from BADC/NEODC.

a good collection of some data, so you don't need do some more checking

A most interesting data set was made available for my research

A nice example of effectiveness that should be followed in other European countries (aka France and Germany)

Accessing the data was very easy. I had various technical questions about the data which were very quickly answered by the helpdesk.

All the data sets are available from the same source.

along with the dataset they are also providing reference intensity plot which i can use for my own results reference

Already covered above but I'd like to re-emphasize the utility of BADC-style resources to 'get to know' datasets, and decide what you really need, even if it is not a BADC dataset! Besides, research focuses change all the time so I could be potentially using BADC data at any time in my career in environmental sciences.

Although metadata has improved and is certainly better than from the original data source, it could still be improved further and sometimes this is a limitation.

An entire piece of research was made possible with the use of data from BADC

ARE YOU FISHING FOR COMPLIMENTS?

As I understood from GO-ESSP meeting, BADC data staff have expertise of both atmospheric science and informatics (metadata technology, in particular). I think it is the strength of BADC.

As mentioned already before. It is quite valuable to have a place where several data sets are collected and can be easily accessed. It helps to see what else is existing besides what one is actually looking for.

As mentioned before, the one stop shop nature of the BADC with unified login, the higher demands of formatting, organisation and documentation of datasets and removing the emphasis on requests to specific individuals has streamlines the data analysis process. I'm much more likely to download a dataset of perceived marginal benefit for comparison, given the easy availability, than if access to these datasets were more trouble.

Assuming it is not run by the scam artists out of East Exe Uni, it would seem a large and high-quality dataset. Data = useful.

BADC is a quick, efficient and controlled way of accessing appropriate data for my academic research. Also the copyright and terms of use are clear.

BADC provides a straight-forward, simple to use, but comprehensive data base for our project.

BADC provides a way of all the data (which is expensive to produce in the first place) to be collected and managed, which may be too costly and difficult for individuals/institutions to do this. By having the data sets well maintained we have the potential to revisit data, do more research with the data and check past results - in my mind this is only done feasibly with a central data centre. In the light of the recent CRU email leak it may become essential to have our data stored and managed well.

Benefits to me - none. However, hopefully, its keeping someone in a job
climate change data sets are most exciting for students to analyse, and also for me to supervise, and have lead to many successful MSc projects under my supervision
compare with other data sets

Comprehensive & complete.

Consistent source of model and reanalysis data used and assessed by multiple parties

Convenience

convenience - although met data are essential it's not the focus of the effort and convenience and ease of access is very important

Data can be accessed quickly; online help with specific questions has been very useful. All my questions have been produced responses from BADC staff.

ease of use

Easier but not frequent update

Easier way to collect the data

easily identification of the data sets

Easy and flexible

easy to access

easy to download

easy, quick to obtain and understand.

ERA-Interim data are only partly available. I need them urgently ;o).

everything in one place

For NCEO, NEODC provides an extremely useful service for some groups by acquiring and making data available efficiently. However many groups also get data from other sources, eg directly from Space Agencies. The scope of NEODC activities must be set against the funding available. They do a great job given the very limited resources at their disposal.

good quality of data available beyond model result

Good quality, reliable, easily available weather data all in one place. Excellent.

good spatial proximity of the data set to the field site

Good time and space coverages

Has provided direct access to northern hemisphere climate data

Having a common place to access data means that the computer programs that I write to process the data can be shared with others who also access this data.

Helpful and efficient BADC helpdesk team.

Hopefully Required dataset is useful to find out the hidden trends and facts to analyse and organise the things effectively in the society

I am aware of other datasets that I have not previously used or known about.

I am extremely thankful to BADC for giving me data which is nearly impossible to procure

I am interested in the work on validation and calibration of satellite. The data set acquired in NCAVEO Field Experiment at Chilbolton is very necessary.

I had the opportunity to address new questions, and the students in my laboratory have improved the quality of their thesis, dissertations and future publications

I have never downloaded data from BADC.

I think it is important for historians and other non-scientists have access to such data.

I think data from BADC/NEODC very useful

I took advantage of another researcher's data stored by BADC by using a small subset of his data holdings. For the little I needed, it would have been too costly to buy the data myself. I am by and large, unaware of the principle researcher's data holdings and reasons for it. I am a fortuitous user of BADC data, but now that I know about it, I may return for more substantial use, depending upon the US Department of Defense's interest in ECMWF data.

I was unable to access the data set as I was unqualified at the time I was interested in using it

I would have liked to know more about how the data was collected and how gaps were filled or how data quality controls are done.

I'm hopeful to be a more active BADC user at some point, if the opportunity arises.

In many instances access to raw data is essential and, although the data sets can be very large, BADC provides this essential tool.

In my opinion these datacentres are absolutely essential and not to support them would be very shortsighted.

Increases the availability of research data

It aids the whole UK atmospheric community, and including international collaboration

It has easy access to global data at no cost which is very useful for researches in Universities.

it has global covering data

It has made obtaining data from other modelling groups fairly straightforward.

It is an excellent medium for collaborative work with colleagues overseas. The access/permissions systems are very well managed and efficient.

it is difficult to compare as the BADC/NEODC has always been present during my time as a researcher

It is exactly the type of data I needed. There are other sources, but it seemed convenient.

it is excellent having a one stop shop!

It is extremely easy to use!

It is free of charge and readily available. You cannot believe that I was made to pay for raw data at a cost of \$10 for every variable per year. and my interest was two variables for 50 years. Worst of all the Data was not as clean as you would get from BADC.

It is improving

It is very difficult to assess data quality or provenance of data before downloading/requesting a dataset. For many datasets summaries and visualisations of the data would allow prospective users of the data to assess whether it may be suitable for their needs. All this should be provided before having to register - for many it is easier to ring/email the originator of the data for this info and while they're at it send it! - Most scientists looking for data probably already know at a personal level the groups/individuals in their field and if the data centre is clunky and difficult to use will bypass it entirely.

It is very essential to carry out high standard research. Its importance is not questionable. **If you could provide your data in a more compressed form to alleviate data transfer problem particularly from third world, then its use world wide in applications for societal increases its importance.**

It is well organized and easy to find what you are looking for.

it keeps me up-to-date on the progress done by the groups/centres that provide observational data sets

It makes it easier to access data as all the different projects are in the same place

it was easy to use, and was exactly the data I needed.

It's better than downloading the CCMVal2 data separately from each of the contributing modelling groups

It's fully supported which means that I can spend less time dealing with technical issues

I've found the data easy to access, the technical information accompanying data sets if good, and I've had prompt, assistance support from the website help e-mail

Large scale data - easily downloadable

Like oceancolor_homepage

Many of my answers to Q21 are my general ideas regarding databases such as BADC. Because I only use BADC to obtain data which I would otherwise have obtained in a different manner, the implications for my own research aren't great.

More data to be freely available.

n/a

n/a

na

no idea

no idea

None

Not at all

Not too much should be read into my answers for very infrequent use. I am registered with BADC (I believe) but have only used any information by proxy and have not included this in my replies.

Owing to the fact that the BADC encourages data producers to adopt common standards and file formats, less effort is generally required when accessing new data sets.

Particularly with regard to BADC, these are no alternative sources for these data: without this service it would not be possible to study the effects of climate in longitudinal studies. **Data from the NEODC enables access to historic records and often avoids the need for new and expensive data collection.**

promote the data-sharing

Quality controlled data

Queries made to BADC online staff are always responded to very promptly, satisfactorily and in a very friendly manner.

Quick and reliable access to the high atmosphere pressure and temperature data

Reliability of technical support

Reliable, easy access

Scientist from Africa could be help access the data in BADC but just obliged to cite them

Secure curation of data is vital - I know of instances where data collected at considerable public expense in the 1980's and 1990's is now sadly no longer available - much to the regret of current researchers.

Secure storage, great for collaborative projects

See comments above

see previous comments

Simply the vast range of data available

Single location means you can find what you want (most of the time).

Single portal.

Some data which the BADC provide are very useful in atmospheric research.

Some of data set are provided for the whole UK...and it cause a lot of time to download and extract for the required area.. it would be grateful if the data set can be extracted for the required data....such as NIMROD data set and Met.Office Surface observation data...

streamlined, no hassle

Thanks a lot

The CLAU data is well kept and hope this access continues.

The CRU TS 3.0 files were easy to access and use.

The Data Extractor is EXTREMELY useful and is a very large reason I access that through BADC. Many thanks for providing it.

The data have been used to Evaluate data-driven techniques for very short range rainfall forecasting.

The data is essential to run undergrad and postgrad projects with a significant research/scientific slant.

The ease of accessing data from one's own PC

The large variety and quantity of data available from the BADC and NEODC, all with a common login and decent documentation makes getting hold of new/additional measurements much simpler than it would otherwise be.

The main dataset used is the (A)ATSR dataset which exists elsewhere, but is almost impossible to access. **The work done by NEODC to make this available in a common format is invaluable.** NEODC needs more datasets like this.

The main problem with BADC is your abysmal, execrable, awful user interface. I often have to download a gigabyte of data to get the two megabytes of data that I need. I beg you, I implore you, take a look at the KNMI user interface at <http://climexp.knmi.nl/start.cgi?someone@somewhere> . Using that interface, I can get exactly the data that I want. I would use more data from BADC if it were not such an unpleasant experience getting data. The data is very good, the coverage is very wide ... but the interface is very, very, very bad.

The rainfall archive has spawned a PhD in its own right - and the outcome of analysis here will probably lead to other PhDs in related areas of climate model validation - all made possible by access to archive data.

The single point of reference with consistent user interface and presentation is convenient.

The support of BADC is essential for the countries like India where the research investment is mainly vested in the government sector. The academic institutions like universities do not have computing facilities for preparing/providing the simulations for understanding the physics part of research requirement. Because this is costly affair and also needs skilled manpower for executing such jobs. The gap region is filled the data centers like BADC, NOAA , NCAR data centers.

the web site is quite easy to use, so the data can be used to explore events or more generic use These data are very useful for applying new data analysis methods and this gives a chance for obtaining completely new results

This is a unique facility which is very important for knowledge creation and policy decision making.

used for developing typical weather data. I could include Europe's typical weather data by using BADC data set

Useful 'one stop shop' for many data sets. Easy access to many data sets.

User-friendly, good support from BADC staff. Sometimes an unreliable online service but a great benefit to all and issues are resolved quickly.

Using data held by BADC means the data is considered robust and the best available, meaning minimal effort is required to justify the use of BADC data in my research.

very convenient and reliable

Very easy and quick to obtain large amounts of good quality data and to merge with other data for comparison

Very fresh high atmospheric temperature data

We can follow the daily development of the polar vortex. The BADC site is very reliable -no significant down time that I can recall (maybe 1 disk crash in all the years ..?) The new (unannounced) levels 0.05,0.01mb (since November) are particularly valuable for us because the lower height limit for our radar data is ~60Km Further height extensions are welcome !

We can well understand the present and future climate with data from BADC.

We compared NCEP, ECMWF and UK Met Office stratospheric assimilations, and, at the time, obtained the most reasonable temperature profiles and air parcel trajectories from the Met Office's product.

Well known access point within the UK community

yearly data series

Yes,I will use the data the same reason as before. That's for more scope of my research.

you know where they (the data) are; they have a kind of "quality stamp"

Can you identify examples of wider impacts (e.g. on society, the economy, policy, etc.) that have resulted from your research, where data accessed from BADC/NEODC has played a significant role?

A major mandate of our department is to understand the effects of environment on fisheries. The HadISST data have allowed a synthesis of interannual variability of SST in the Labrador Sea that has been useful in ecosystem studies carried out by colleagues.

A paper is in progress where I use the data to evaluate terrestrial habitability (www.astrobiology-upra.org).

A recent example is the use of coastal wind data (from MIDAS) in developing high resolution (200m scale) indices of wave fetch. This allows predictive mapping of biological communities in shallow areas of coast, and may have contributed to the recent Defra Marine Datalayers project. The datalayers are likely to be used in planning MPAs. Burrows, M. T., R. Harvey, and L. Robb. 2008. Wave exposure indices from digital coastlines and the prediction of rocky shore community structure. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 353:1-12. doi: 10.3354/meps07284.

ALTHOUGH I AM STILL IN THE RESEARCH STAGE, SHOULD THE CONCLUSIONS PRODUCED FROM YOUR DATA PROVE VALID, IT WILL ALLOW FOR A STABILISING AND CONTROL OF GLOBAL CLIMATE SUFFICIENT TO ALLOW FOR LARGE SCALE AGRICULTURAL INVESTMENT IN AN AREA THAT PREVIOUSLY COULD NOT JUSTIFY ANY NOTABLE DEGREE OF CAPITAL INPUT. SIMILARLY FOREWARD PLANNING FOR ENERGY PRODUCTION AND DISTRIBUTION CAN BE BETTER GEARED TO MEET THE GENERAL NEEDS OF OUR POPULATION, LASTLY A REDUCTION OR EVEN REVERSAL OF HUMAN MIGRATION PATTERNS AND FAIRER DISTRIBUTION OF WEALTH.

Anything associated with improved weather forecast accuracy.

As BADC provides free ECMWF data to UK academics it allows us to have a unique dataset over other countries doing research who will likely have to gather similar data elsewhere. This allows for scientific comparisons in the use of different datasets that are used as inputs into models and thus a better understanding of the subject.

As I said, I've just begun to use these data

At current moment, I am only using this data, so I still can not compare to others data

BADC has provided dataset which has allowed me to put my project into functionality, which will help the society know the climate better before hand

BADC is contributing to establishing a global infrastructure in 189 countries through the WMO WIS initiative

basic sciences

benefit to academic/research community

Better prediction of energy use/production

Century-length analysis of climate change on coral reefs.

climate change

Climate change studies. The results based on BADC data sets are more convincing.

Correlation with SST data of population dynamics of endangered species - enables better management
CRU data

Currently I have an article accepted for publication that calculates thermal expansion contribution to sea level change from sea surface temperature data.

Data housed at BADC will be used in the WMO SPARC CCMval report and WMO Ozone report

Data is being used in decision making by the private sector. Government is reluctant to embrace the idea.

Energy saving of Building, Zero CO2

estimation of changes in storm risk in climate scenario simulations

Explanation of climate change projections in the context of observation data

extended knowledge of maritime history

forecasting on electricity loading that are very useful for national grid producers

further research, findings to analyse

Global Weather Observations and controlling the global warming

Government have decided not to fund research into Amplitude Modulation Noise from Wind Farm as this is a relatively minor noise problem within the wider context of noise annoyance. The MIDAS wind data statistics of stations close to a wind farm were very important to make an estimate of the severity of the problem at that specific wind farm.

Hard to say!

Hard, because of limitation raised above. Most data are access for scientist in Europe, therefore US data center are more easy to access

I am a designer of low carbon techniques and am hampered by the availability of data that I have paid for through tax.

I am currently working on coastal erosion and sediment release from cliff systems. The NextMap data are very important inputs to cliff elevation, and help with prediction of future volumes. The rainfall data provide highly useful inputs to model cliff hydrology

i am investigating adaptation of ash to climate change. Ash is deeply dormant and needs an extended chill period. BADC has enabled me to look at this requirement from Inveness to the Pyrenees. Current reforestation policy requires the use of local seed. My research shows that this is a flawed concept.

The work is funded by the forestry commission and we hope to help alter this policy in light of climate change.

I cannot assess this at present as my work is ongoing, but I hope that its output (namely online educational materials about climate change) will be of benefit to a wider audience than just scientists, e.g. policymakers, businesses, general public etc

I have been able to establish a relationship between increase in air pollution and the increase in respiratory illness in England

I have been looking into winter precipitation variability over the East Anglian region of Britain, my results would be of use to many groups of people, e.g. weather forecasters and hydrologists.

I have used the BADC data (in combination with Defra sheep density data and CEH land cover data) to assess the risk of sheep scab, a disease in sheep, in the UK. Such models can be used to better target disease management programmes where they are needed most- in the hotspot areas.

I have used the data from BADC to produce journal papers and technical reports submitted to the Scottish Government that have helped inform policy and planning.

I have worked with 50years of BADC data, tree ring data and galactic cosmic radiation data and have published a paper 3 months ago, which is already twice cited.

I hope that BADC help me to produce a more exhaustive conference site

I think by citing your data others become aware of it and access it if they need to.

I use BADC data for DEFRA projects whose outcome is used to inform policy.

I used the data from BADC to prove (in a year 1999 article) that global warming influences earth rotation

I used the EMCWF back trajectory and reanalysis products to examine the role of meteorology in pollution transport in Northern Europe, in particular the UK region. This established that pollution over the UK was enhanced during periods associated with continental European outflow.

I used the to study the processes leading to predictability for a convective event. In the long run, a very long one, the impacts will be related to the improvement in the forecast at the convective scale. So overall far in time and quite generic.

I was able to predict drought in England in the 1990s a year ahead and drought in India 5 years ahead
Study of temperature in England in the 1800s I am able to predict sharp cooling and rapid fluctuations in temperature at present and through the next 30 years in response to similar inactive sun.

Identified increasing trend in outage rates on microwave telecommunications links. This requires a complete replanning of the regulation of the spectrum in the UK.

I'm not in research and have never downloaded data from BADC.

Impacts of the conducted hydrological change study in the catchment may have potential implications on local ecology and habitat.

Improve our understanding of meteorology and help to improve forecast

Improved Scottish flood prediction service using met data for Loich | Linnhe area

In air pollution studies

In general the improvement of climate model simulations, which results in better climate predictions which in turn is what society needs to plan the future.

In my case, It helped to compare climate wind variability of observations and operational NWP models
In my research the existing 15 min rainfall records are very limited, so alternative data were required. The Met.Office Surface observation data provide more dense network of daily rainfall which was able to improve the model performances..

In the future I will be working on the effect of climate change on health so there are policy/social implications there.

Increasing concern about the productivity of golden eagles in the west of Scotland (May rainfall) and how this relates to the significance of persecution in the east of Scotland

Influence of climatic warming on conservation of rare mountain plants

Inter-European legislation and verification of weather conditions on next to real-time.

Investigation of woodland phenology by Forestry Research

IPCC should use your data!

It allowed to give decision makers more accurate results of impacts of climate change, leading to more effective adaptation and mitigation measures.

It has helped develop models of vegetation productivity used in decision support tools for setting upland grazing regimes.

It has helped to improve our numerical modelling of meteorological processes.

It is not possible to quantify this as I have not yet completed my PhD.

It is very difficult say at present. But if BADC support is not there means , I feel research will suffer understanding of science.

It was compared to other data to minimize errors. It was useful but had it not been available then little would have changed

Journal publication

Key Stakeholders (Government)

Looked at ways to mitigate climate change. Looked at phenological changes.

LST by satellite data have the potential to show the surface temperature over the whole global surface (and not only over insitu measurement points). This can be very helpful for the climate research, but also - in smaller scales - for LST changes after anthropogenic impacts on the scenery (de- and reforestation, urbanization,...).

modelling climate change

Most environmental phenomena are affected by the impact of climate and climatic change. Access to a time series of weather station records from BADC has enabled this impact to be quantified: this would not have been possible without BADC.

Much of our work is related to Carbon budgets and climate change, we use weather data/derived climate data to inform growth of the forested area of GB. We also look into the effects of climate on the spread of diseases and pests which affect trees.

My climate change related research should ultimately benefit the wider society, and BADC data has played an important role in developing the models involved

My research aims at the more efficient management of the electromagnetic spectrum in the presence of atmospheric effects and is of relevance to telecom industry as well as regulatory bodies like ITU and OFCOM.

My research tends to conclude with recommendations for conservation of species and habitats

My research using BADC data has helped direct conservation efforts for NGOs working to protect two different bird species.

My studies on the impact of weather / climate on the dynamics of freshwater lakes have proved of interest to regulators working on a European as well as National level.

New data models and standards developed have been influenced significantly by BADC data, and are in turn influencing approaches being taken by WMO, INSPIRE and other international activities.

NO, email provided below if you want a case study of how to limit access!

No. I can tell you that - without you and other similars - we would be hearing/seeing only what powerful others (with bias) would like us to see. I can analyse - if the analysis is available. YOU SHOULD CONTINUE - FREEDOM OF DATA PRODUCTION IS IMPORTANT.

Not yet, but in time.. Emma Ferranti's PhD on spatial and temporal changes in rainfall in Cumbria has all sorts of societal and policy implications. (I supervise Emma)

on society, the economy and creation of future government policy.

on society, the economy, policy...

on the economy

Only at the local level - use of BADC data to help explain physical behaviour of estuaries to equip local groups with information ref: consequences of dredging or channel straightening

Ozone layer problems have a graet impact over the ecologists.

policy implications and alternatives for gov't

Policy, society and Environment (air pollution)

Potential for better understanding of public health issues.

provides evidence for the use of vitamin D supplementation in pregnancy.

Re. question 24. I would not say our research is high impact , but we are willing to collaborate in a

case study. Alan Manson is the leader of our group, so I have added his e-mail address and phone number.

Research based on BADC data has bearings on climate effecting atmospheric water content and satellite communications.

Research feeds into climate research at UK Met Office which has benefits for society.

Research feeds into interventions to reduce climate change impacts, e.g. Department of Health heat-health warning system.

Research on the ozone hole, and its year to year variations and relation to Polar Stratospheric Clouds. Research on volcanic plumes in the stratosphere. The discovery that supercell thunderstorms enabled smoke from large boreal forest fires to breach the buoyancy barrier at the tropopause and enter and remain in the stratosphere.

Research on wind power resource for renewable hydrogen production has been presented at industry and government sponsored conferences and has received positive feedback

Research papers e.g. on solar influence on climate have been employed by the Met Office for policy decisions and have been quoted in science reports for the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. Nearly all of my papers involve data from BADC/NEODC in some way.

Scientific publication

See website: <http://speleotrove.com/weather/>
society

Society through research dissemination

Some of my research on contamination of Private Water Supplies in Scotland used rainfall data from BADC and this research is now embedded in legislation

Some of the data has contributed to research that has informed EA policy

sustainable historic buildings and collections

The 1-degree latitude-longitude SST data is useful for studies of how the winds influence upwelling and the environment for fish.

The archived data from NEODC helps to model the sand dune dynamics in time, which helps us to understand the coastal environment. The result may contribute to climate change research and local conservation management.

The availability of a large satellite database has permitted to implement and make available real-time data exploitation techniques to access to the entire satellite database

the availability of project data source images hosted by BADC has opened notable opportunities for a wide range of academic activities

The BADC data has allowed me to complete the evaluation of IPCC AR4 models considering circulation types classifications

The data has enabled a wider understanding of water resource issues for wetland environments that are very important in current programmes of increasing or restoring wetland areas and climate change

The data contributed to a study and a publication of on the spatial distribution of radioactive fallout in Northern Ireland from the Chernobyl nuclear accident of 1986. This work has provided baseline data which may in the future inform planning policy with regard to nuclear development and/or monitoring of fallout in N Ireland.

The data from the Nimrod dataset I use via BADC access enable validation of my own precipitation products. This allows me to provide algorithms for satellite rainfall estimation to public bodies, such as Civil Protection, Met Services, etc... Validated data are essential and BADC is helping me to have an impact on societal use of my products.

The data was to supplement others

The data were used for research on changes in vegetation affected by changes in land use. This is work for Defra and MoD and may impact on future government policy.

The Hadley A1FI dataset corresponds most closely with the data developed by Sokolov et al. (2009, J. Climate, 22), which is likely the best most recent forecast. But the Sokolov data do not have the resolution that the Hadley A1FI data have and downscaling the Sokolov data would introduce a wider set of uncertainties than using the Hadley data. The main point is that while the A1FI SRES was once considered an extreme and rather unrealistic possibility, we now know it is the most likely scenario in the absence of effective policy intervention--the benefits of which would not manifest for perhaps 5-6 decades due to inertia, if implemented at all. It's been important and effective to show the likely biotic responses to the changes in climate that are expected under this now more likely and robust scenario. I have been able to show that landscape and regional impacts are expected to be more extensive and

manifest sooner than had been expected under the A1 or A2 SRES discussed in IPCC A4. This is beginning to get serious traction with funding agencies and NGOs.

The main thing is with student projects. The ability to analyze real data is invaluable for students who are learning the field.

The models are developed aim to help the understanding of water and pollutant flows through the environment and the changes in biogeochemical cycling resultant from land-use management and climate changes. These models help to assess the quality of our water resources. Without the BADC/NEODC data resource it would be far harder to find and format the driving data for these models.

The MODIS 1B data are very useful in atmospheric correction.

The objective of exploring the use of data-driven models (DDM) as integrators of radar rainfall information and numerical weather prediction model for rainfall prediction.

The outcome of my research, will hopefully help improve policy on Particulate Matter monitoring.

Different parameters including weather influence particle size, without accessing met information, I would not have been able to discuss discrepancies between different types of monitors used to monitor PM.

the policy maker could get some information from our results

The possibility for our papers and presentations to show trustworthy information about the trends of global warming in the Gulf of California, has provided excellent tools for NGOs and park managers to call attention to the situation the marine fauna is facing.

The RAPID programme had clear links to policy through Knowledge Exchange with DECC / Defra / UKCIP / MCCIP

The research I am carrying out is related to climate change mitigation and adaptation. Therefore there is a high probability of the research outcomes impacting on society, policy, technology and the economy.

The risk group at Lloyd's of London has shown interest in modelling of landfall for tropical storms

the same with the above.

This is mainly for academic project work(BSc, MSc, PhD). We have used the data for coastal impacts of extreme waves and surges on the south coast of UK.

This is still very much in its infancy but the SCIMAP project on which I have been working has begun to influence land management practices to reduce diffuse pollution.

This study is useful to eradicate the water shortage in my country. If government and policy makers want to do something for it rather debating on television

To be determined

to calibrate beijing-1 satellite.

To have good climate impact assessment, model output data need to be assessed for probable biases. So we need to collect observation-based data. We do our collection activities in Asia, but we also need European data.

to understand the reasons for climate behaviour

UKCP09 - web enabled custom outputs generated through remote server calls

UKMO model is among the atmosphere models that simulates the Indian Monsoon better. So data initialise this model essential for research.

Ultimately, the research could provide advice on operational mechanisms for the energy supply

industry; provide better wind forecasting and characterisation of wind fields for planning reasons.

Understanding the historical background of current climate debates.

Unfortunately the ISAMS data for NO was not good enough to do much with but it had the potential to affect what we knew about the Ozone hole. which has impact in many areas.

Use of ATSR data in heatwave analysis (previous and ongoing).

Use of chemistry-climate model projections in WMO/UNEP ozone assessments

Using the skills of BADC staff we have been able to make important datasets collected by the Carbon Trust widely available, and are currently preparing a proposal to enhance UKERC's Energy Data Centre

Validation of climate model runs for my country

We are still in the process of using these data to correlate with the behaviour of marine mammals but we hope it will enable us to more accurately predict the behaviour of animals and the impact increased

human activity in the ocean (noise, increased marine renewable energy sources) will have on the management and conservation of the species. We're not yet in a position to help you with a case study but hopefully in future.

We are using precipitation data to find relationships between climate change and agricultural production.

We are very excited about the role NEODC/BADC might play in developing and being the custodian for Essential Climate Variables, especially facilitating the cross comparison of data sets. We are also looking forward to their role as custodians of IPCC CMIP data. They are currently custodians of UKCIP data - this all shows a growing role in climate issues.

NCEO is supportive of these efforts.

We are working toward improved understanding of intrinsic climate variability and development of better conceptual models of past and likely future regional climate fluctuations in the context of rising anthropogenic forcing. Social/economic consequences in terms of better response and enhanced resilience to climate change in future are enormous.

We can understand the terrestrial carbon cycle better.

We have been able to demonstrate that the expansion of woodland cover does not pose a threat to water availability and this has the potential to result in many social and environmental benefits.

We have performed climate change simulations that have been used to conduct studies on many different aspects (local economy, tourism, coastal management, energy, ...). The models used to perform the climate change simulations have been validated and their performance improved using data accessed from BADC/NEODC

We use data in the Caripanda Project in Italy, to study climate change in glacierized area where there is a strong anthropization of the environment. The social and political part took part of the process to determine the future scenarios in the area.

We use hadcm3 data to explain the changes of water use efficiency and crop productivity in the future in North China Plain

We were able to provide evidence how and where the easterly waves over Africa are generated. This has, in a way, challenged earlier assumption about wave generation.

Where researchers have used the databases and rechecked/cleaned the data it would be beneficial for these sets to be redistributed on BADC rather than repeat work being carried out by many individuals yes. Firstly, Access to data/information is vital. It is assumed that only 'professional' people know - but evidence indicates these are mainly chair bound - and few take to the field. Hence the growing reliance on models. Second, some countries have made access to data/information difficult. This is done for reasons that include 'give value to science', and 'user pay'. Last year it was possible to demonstrate to an audience in NZ what can be obtained, and its usefulness in explaining natural land form processes.

Please provide any further comments you would like to make regarding any 'very satisfied' or 'very dissatisfied' ratings

A bulletin section under your account showing recent changes to your subscribed data sets would be a nice feature.

A lot of the data should be more freely available

A wider range of sensor would be useful i.e. airborne gamma

access limitation for scientist in developing countries is the weakest link

Again, the technical support has always been very good.

All data should be freely available without data locks etc. Science is a united human endeavour, not a commercial business.

All left blank as I never download data from BADC.

Although access to "restricted" datasets was granted reasonably quickly, I'm not really certain why it was restricted in the first place.

Annabelle and Graham at the BADC helpdesk have been enormously helpful over the past 2 years.

Any problems encountered are greatly outweighed by access to such a wide range of data.

As I very rarely use the service it is hard to comment or have firm feelings on the ratings

Available data with long temporal coherence

BADC offer access to unique data.

Changes are often made to the dataset I use that affect my processing without my being informed; however I believe this fault lies with the data provider and not the BADC (often the BADC appears not to have known about the changes either).

Costs are minimal

Could we be emailed when new data is added to the datasets we are subscribed to. Especially corrections to data could go unnoticed otherwise

Data is good and regularly updated. Helpdesk staff very helpful, quick to respond to issues and keep you informed of progress.

Data is very relevant, inexpensive and easy to access and download.

Description of datasets and navigation between them is poor. Examples of data would be beneficial to allow a decision to be made on whether the data is of the nature required before applying for access.

Do not access data with sufficient regularity to become familiar with the downloading procedures.

Excellent free resource

FAAM metadata is poor and always has been. In addition, it would be good to be notified of changes e.g. r0 to r1. The BADC must know I've downloaded the dataset so surely I could automatically be emailed maybe?

For a novice in meteorology I just wanted lists of what I would have thought are straightforward datasets; ie daily sunshine, temp, run-of-wind and precipitation, by a dozen UK regions, over a given time-span. But I needed to spend ages poring over maps and trying to find several stations that could give each element as they don't all collect the same stats, or for aligned periods. A messy and slow affair. I'm surprised there is no aggregated single dataset for the many potential users like myself out there.

For me it was very useful during the time I required the most and I was very satisfied.

For the (limited number of) datasets I use it's all there, easy to find. An invaluable resource - thanks! free access to the data is vital

Free availability of BADC data are a fantastic resource!

Free of charge!

generally very happy

Generally, I get satisfied but I would like you to re-consider monitoring location and its density.

The HelpDesk have been particularly helpful when encountering difficulties with the Data Extractor

Help desk always helpful

Helpdesk has always been very helpful indeed.

Helpdesk has been extremely helpful in directing me to data I need, and dealing with access issues.

Helpdesk staff have been extremely helpful

Helpful and knowledgeable staff

High atmospheric temperature data precision

I am always impressed by the speed of response with respect to individual queries about data availability.

I am currently having free access to the SST data, which is very useful to my research.

I am frustrated that I can only access NextMap data from NEODC via my research students (NERC studentships). I would like to see access granted to supervisors of NERC students for whom this data is required such that we are both able to examine datasets independently.

I am impressed

I can never find what I want on BADC without going round in circles for ages first. The navigation makes no sense to me whatsoever. In fact I'm only doing this questionnaire now because I couldn't figure out how to download the data I was after!

I cite the BADC as an example of what a national data center ought to look (and act) like.

I consider the 1 degree surface temperature data for the satellite period of record the BEST in the world.

I could not answer anything but "neutral" because I am largely unaware of the nature and reason for BADC's existence. I was just lucky they had a few days of data that I needed to try to prove a point.

I downloaded free data and the helpdesk were very responsive to my needs

I find the navigation through the available datasets quite confusing

I have always found the BADC team to be exceptionally helpful.

I have still not received any dataset that I had asked from BADC for my project work.

I have the impression from the way the data are formatted etc that you need more/better people with database skills. I sometimes feel I could do much better myself with MySQL/Apache. Access to MIDAS data is erratic, unreliable and poorly organised. Does BADC use data themselves - I get the impression you don't, at least not much

I rarely use the metadata, so I had to guess about the quality of curation

I really appreciate the service BADC provides. It is so easy to download data and costs much less time than I experienced with other webpages where data is distributed.

I was after weather data from various stations in UK and France. This was not easy to find,, and often data missing

I wish MIDAS data for the previous year could be made available in Jan/Feb. Also, far too few stations have any wind gusts data :-).

I would like to have access to weather data between 2004-2008.

If I have needed data, you generally have it available, and the quality is good, thanks

I'm not sure its BADC's fault but the data I wanted was a poor data set and so it was not properly "finished off" or curated

in general I'm satisfied with the data

Individual researchers are excluded - by cost (and when funding is so restricted it is inexcusable) - or by not belonging to a team.

Is the first place where I begin to search

It is an excellent facility.

It is easy to get the data and the data server is fast.

It is really easy to obtain the data at no cost, I appreciate it very much

it is very difficult to find out which met stations record the data i am interested in - essentially you have to download data for several until you find one that does (I need radiation data)

JOHN SNOW WAS ABLE TO CONDUCT AN EPIDEMIOLOGY OF CHOLERA IN LONDON SUFFICIENT TO PROVIDE AN EXACT CAUSE OF THE DISEASE, THUS BE ABLE TO BOTH STOP THE EPIDEMIC, PREVENT FURTHER OUTBREAKS, ALLOW FOR FURTHER RESEARCH AND PROVIDE USEFUL ADVICE FOR FUTURE MAJOR INFRASTRUCTURE PROJECTS. THE PROVISION OF ACCURATE INFORMATION/DATA ALLOWS FOR SUCH MASSIVE BENEFITS TO BE PRODUCED. IT IS THRU SUCH AGENCIES AS BADC CAN SIMILAR ADVANCES BE MADE IN THE REALMS OF GLOBAL CLIMATE CHANGE AND MORE LOCALISED CLIMATIC ISSUES.

Keeping the data free for download makes it extremely accessible.

Makes life so much easier, can get on with other research.

Metadata could sometimes be better

More data to be freely available.

Most data is free and kept updated which is important.

My attempt to get data was basically frustrated by the bureaucracy. I would attempt to use the data base if I believed it was possible for me.

Navigation is tricky at best, and confusing at worst. There is no option to download data in blocks from an experiment. A simple, tick this box and move on to select multiple files would be incredibly useful.

NB. DATA ARE PLURAL

not good for current/very recent periods, a lot of omissions and a fair amount of data cleaning required

One area that I think might be improved is the extraction of data, for example the MIDAS data. I had to do quite a bit of work to produce a spatial data set from the MIDAS data set, and station location files which were not all in the formats described in the user manuals - which also were not so simple to find. This is really quite a tricky issue to solve, but somehow the supporting information could be better organised.

Overall I am impressed with the data service

Quality checks on MIDAS rainfall data appear to be incomplete and very subjective with many errors of multiday totals (not reported) or missing decimal places creeping in.

Re cost 'very satisfied': it was free. Re comprehensiveness 'dissatisfied': this was because the rainfall data we needed was not measured and recorded in enough locations (at the time, 1986) to be very useful for comparing with our other data (detailed terrestrial gamma-radiation data).

Retrieving ERA-40 data is very problematic; There is no tool to reduce the resolution and combine all data in 1 file. In comparison, NCEP-NCAR reanalysis data are much easier to download and use.

Some data is stored on the BADC with no metadata

Something more needs to be done about people storing incorrect data on validated data bases. As modellers, we have had several problems with using data from a validated data store on BADC which turn out later (after many wasted hours) to have associated problems. Also, there are problems with campaign data sets with some groups using local time and others using GMT and not enough info in the headers. A general comment would be that headers should be checked by somebody from BADC before they are submitted to the final validated data base. There is a large amount of variation between such headers, with some groups providing all necessary information (what 1,2, and 3 mean in missing data columns for instance) whilst other groups leave you to guess.

Sometimes the process of acquiring and downloading data seems a bit 'flaky'

Support have been very helpful with queries.

terrible slow, buggy data engine. Appears to be 10 years out of date in terms of methods of data mining, processing etc. Desparately needs a radical redesign to aid navigation, explanations, access to data etc.

Thank you so much for providing the data. It is so very important.

The availability of very low cost data to academic researchers, and particularly to doctoral students, allows experimentation in the early phases of research that would likely be considered too costly and therefore risky if the data involved were expensive or difficult to obtain.

The BADC has fully met my needs so far.

The BADC helpdesk is fantastic, they are very friendly and have solved every problem I had 100%.

The BADC is much less comprehensive in its holdings of climate data than some US datasources. It would be nice if everything was available from one site rather than having to search around the world for what you need. Unfortunately, BADC often doesn't have duplicates of datasets held elsewhere. The BADC version of the MIDAS dataset is very poorly structured. Data cleaning (removing duplicate and erroneous values) took a large amount of research time. There are no unique identifiers (primary keys) for observations and there is duplication in all fields making database construction challenging. Frustratingly, it is clear that this data is held in a database by the UK Met Office, yet is only provided to BADC users as a series of spreadsheets.

The data I received was free.

The data resolution is sufficient enough to my research work. Providing many data sets free of cost for academic research activities is a must in current trend. BADC is in the front line in that service. Hence I feel very satisfied in such aspects.

The data we are using have no cost and the information on data base is sent regularly by email.

The data were free, the data centre had what I required and the helpdesk was very helpful!

The email support/help provided is always very quick and efficient.

The FORMAT of reading the DATASET (i.e. netCDF) and algorithms used are quite unsatisfactory or not provided. This need to be looked into I suppose

The ftp technology and basic user interface seem quite dated and are not the most user friendly

The guidance and assistance provided by the helpdesk was very quick when the data extractor was playing up. Much appreciated!

the help given when e-mailing about a problem was very useful as the helpdesk replied very quickly with the data i needed, rather than giving instructions of how to find it, which saved a lot of time.

The main problem met was that of a rather confusing approach to get the data available for downloading. However, when asking for help, the problems were rapidly solved.

The methodology used to develop this data is convincing and gives me the confidence, and the researchers associated with this data are reknowned

The NEODC staff have been extremely helpful.

The provision of data in common, easy-to-read formats goes a long way towards making multidisciplinary research possible. Today I had email from a behavioral ecologist (from the UK) who wanted ocean chlorophyll data. Without data centers like BADC, this person wouldn't stand a chance of making any progress on his/her work. It may not be sexy, but data centers like the BADC are a fundamental component of multidisciplinary science infrastructure.

the resource enables study that would otherwise be of .too difficult' access

The size limit on downloading data from the data extractor makes it impossible to use for any significant data sets. The directory structure makes it hard to ftp the data en mass. Because of this I

no longer use BADC regularly to obtain data relying on other sources for the data.

The staff have always been brilliant when datasets have "gone down" and have fixed the problem very quickly. The administration of getting access is also always quick and the helpful reminders that access rights need renewing help to maintain continuous access to the data I need.

The standard met sites provide excellent data of known high quality and without this route, it would be necessary to buy each record individually from the met office, without knowing if it would be useful - and it would be very hard to make geographic trend statements or comparisons

The support and ease to which data is made available is great and hope this good service will continue in the future.

The support team is really helpful and have so far solved any encountered problem promptly

The support to some questions was very fast, and accurate.

The UK met data is updated rather sporadically and one cannot rely on getting relevant data quickly

The website can be slow. I have had problems getting "missing data" which did exist "at source", but overall - a good service.

There is generally no assessment/screening of data quality meaning that the user has to make judgements and spend time essentially duplicating the effort

This is a wonderful, free resource. Long may it continue.

To access LiDAR and air photography data you have to have a prior knowledge of the areas in which surveys have taken place especially to find the data outside the UK (the map search facility is good, but not up-to-date the last time I looked) - I know the NEODC team are working on this very hard at the moment. In the past finding LiDAR data has been hard, but the NEODC team are tackling this and creating an up-to date archive.

Useful, quickly available data sets make me a very satisfied user.

Very comprehensive and time-extended atmospheric analysis made almost realtime

very satisfied

very satisfied

We just download the stratospheric analyses. It is great to have daily updates- so we can follow the evolution of the winter polar vortex. Re data updates - changes- I received nothing from BADC about the new (Nov 2009) pressure levels. One of my programs noticed them. It was a pleasant surprise! (but still a surprise). My access is by ftp. I have not looked for other data sets. I am not sure I have access to other sets, I am not sure there are other sets in which I would have a present interest. Cost is a big consideration- we couldn't afford to buy.

Well, it's a lot of data. Data =useful.

When I downloaded the MIDAS precipitation data, no extractor existed. I spent several weeks to extract the relevant long stations from the files (even though I used self-written extraction software).

Furthermore, the data were full of gaps and nobody at BADC or the MetOffice could explain these gaps. Hope this has changed in the meanwhile...

When I had a difficulty extracting data the first time I used BADC, I received a prompt and helpful reply.

When I met some difficulties during using the data,I always got the help in time.

Would like a greater density of coverage of weather stations and weather data in the UK

Please describe any problems you have encountered in identifying, accessing and / or obtaining data from BADC/NEODC.

1.The search engine was not working. 2. Some of the readme file does not give essential information about the data.

A clearer understanding of the formatting of some of the data, as well as a discussion with the user about which data format is the most suitable would be greatly appreciated.

A question directed via email has never been answered, but I have not actively pursued this.

Accessing data is an issue

Accessing UK met data is straightforward. Accessing global met data, especially in remote locations such as South Georgia, Antarctic was more troublesome as I didn't know which dataset to search.

All data sets have been available when requested, so no problems encountered

Already highlighted

ARSF data catalogue and access still a bit clunky

As alluded above, whilst the data service is excellent overall, the Data Extractor software is sometimes hard to access

As mentioned before, there are some problems with the ERA-Interim data visibility.

BADC customer support was excellent. As I work in a similar data center here in the US, I was very impressed.

BADC didn't want to give me any data - I found what I wanted elsewhere for free

Climate data should be freely available upon registering an email address but potential users should NEVER be vetted for appropriate use or affiliation.

Collecting data frequency is different at each of monitoring sites. (e.g. can you describe daily monitoring station or hourly monitoring station?)

confusing at times

Confusing to obtain the data I desired

Crashed data requests, temporary non-availability of data, delays in updates, difficulty in identifying monitoring points.

Data access was very good, registering and accessing data was very straight forward and well documented.

Data are not available for NGO-based researchers - only through my Edinburgh University affiliation, was I able to access data.

Data Extractor can be sluggish and/or temperamental.. But Help Desk are very good at responding to queries and if needs be extracting data on behalf of user.

Data extractor is not available for certain datasets e.g. 11-member RCM dataset.

data extractor not working or too slow

Data extractor was seemingly always broken when first trying to obtain data sets

Data format (surface temperatures & precipitation) difficult to process and interpret. Requires extensive manipulation & restructuring to produce a selected dataset suitable for statistical analysis

Deciphering directory names like "aebtg" made it difficult to locate the specific values being sought.

Descriptions are unclear if you are not trained in the field for which data was acquired.

Descriptions of data columns could be better

Details escape me, last time I used the system was a few months ago but then it could be a bit frustrating

Downloading as zip file saves much space and download time, but is hard to work out how to do that for a single file.

Files of large volume to be processed in a PC.

For the MSG2 SEVIRI data there is only 5 out of 12 channels available for the LRIT, I also failed to find instruction or description of this data hence I have not been able to use it yet.

FTP directories disappear or get moved around at random, without warning. Sometimes data is inaccessible for several days at a time.

get multiple files with "mget" in ftp

Have sometimes taken several attempts to get data extractor to process request

the constant problem with the Data Extractor. The data obtained from MetOffice -MIDAS data set required an additional extensive quality control. When BADC was contacted by e-mail the replies were very quick and very helpful.

I downloaded data from UKMO for 2006 and had the problem that the data only contained missing values or zero. However, I am not sure yet if they are in the wrong manner on the BADC webpage or if something went wrong while I downloaded the data. I will soon try it again and if I still have no real data in the files I will contact you.

I find the data extractor unreliable. There is also a lot of post processing of data involved as I need to produce a daily time series and there are many days on which there are multiple values - it takes some time to filter out the best value.

I found it quite difficult (or at least time-consuming) to identify the set containing the data I was looking for. Perhaps a better grouping of the sets available would help. Assessing them was fairly easy once I found the right sets.

I found it difficult to navigate to the particular data set I required

I had difficulties importing the data into ArcGis. Eventually I needed to code the data and manipulate it so I could use it in Arc Map. This took 3 extra weeks of work but it eventually worked.

I had difficulty because there were single days data missing from the observations of daily temperature and it was not clearly flagged.

I had trouble with the rainfall radar data from BADC but it was a long time ago and after trying briefly I dropped it in favour of a simpler solution.

I have found difficulty in finding and downloading rainfall data, it just seems too clunky and not that intuitive when looking for data. difficult to identify exactly the right station that has sufficient run of data I have had some problems with the identification names of the datasets. It is not very clear from which experiment the data proceed.

I have sometimes known that a survey has been done, but NEODC hadn't got the LiDAR data - as I said above they are working to amend this and are doing a great job under challenging circumstances.

I have tried to obtain GCM data from BADC. This is extremely tedious because individual fields of interest are folded in with other fields so an inordinate amount of time was spent downloading the data. A data extraction facility similar to those used in other centres would be very welcome.

I need a fresh password to access the data set again.

I occasionally forget my password, (and once forgot I was registered) but the help desk always helps me out.

I often find large unexplained gaps in the data sets (rainfall etc), presumably due to measurer absence/change of circumstance - a note/code to explain this might be useful.

I quite often cannot download data directly from the database, but it is always delivered at some point later via email

I was having problems opening downloads from the site due to the firewall settings on my computer however when I contacted BADC about this problem before I knew what was causing it I received no reply

I was hoping to have access to daily data but unfortunately this is not yet possible

I was searching for a brief description of how data is assimilated and what are the inputs, assumptions, models used and stuff. It would be helpful for beginners like me to know about the data, before we start using it.

I would add that it would benefit BADC staff not to have to archive data purely for box-ticking purposes. My impression (from speaking to my PDRAs) is that BADC staff are severely overworked and are unable to provide much useful support in putting model data into the appropriate formats. My comments in general should be viewed in the context of someone who has mainly provided rather than downloaded BADC data - it seems that the questionnaire is focused almost entirely around the latter.

I would prefer the data set (I am referring to the data set I used) not to be arranged several files (one decade per file)--an additional file should be included that contains the whole timeseries.

I'd like to have an register access. But my request couldn't be accepted in 2007.

Identifying relevant observation stations for wind data for a certain period in a specific area was very slow and difficult in places.

If the name of specific data sets is not known it can be hard to locate them

I'm a bit disappointed by the lack of support for some of the data. In particular, I am unable to properly analyze the NIMROD radar data because nobody seems to know how to put this data onto a latitude/longitude grid. Surely somebody out there should know how to do this. The BADC help site did not lead to a resolution of this problem.

In my case the speed of our own network connection was a limitation factor.

In the case of (A)ATSR data, the navigation and download functionality is impossibly cumbersome and time consuming if you want to download large volumes of data from multiple dates. Problem solved by Helpdesk, but the web interface should make this easier.

incompactability of Connectivity & data volume especially in third world internet speed

ISAMS data was supposed to have included NO but that aspect of it was poorly determined and so it was not "properly" included in the data base and I had to go through circuitous routes to get hold of what there was. It may have been the experimenters supplying the data to the BDC which caused this though rather than BADC itself.

it is a bit tedious to pull out foreign windspeed data from the midas dataset; I usually end up downloading a large file (eg Asian data for 2005) and extracting data manually from this (might be my fault for not reading the manual?)

it is not always very easy to identify station codes and access specific data

it is not easy to identify what is actually in a dataset without downloading sample data and hunting

through the metadata for clues

It is overloaded and the required soft ware is not readily available. I have to resort to Matlab for solution

it was difficult to compile data for more than 1 period (year)

It would be fantastic if the data extractor used for UK Midas data could be extended to the global dataset. All I want to do is extract weather data for 1 rain gauge in Australia and it's taken me 2 days! It would be good if the data were available in e.g. *.txt format, rather than *.nc etc., which are difficult for non-physical oceanographers to deal with

It would be useful to be able to automatically inform all users who have downloaded a dataset that a new revision of that dataset is available

It would be very useful if the SST and SLP data that are used broadly in the climate science community (HadISST and HadSLP) were updated more regularly, a two month delay in HadISST limits its application to seasonal-interannual problems.

Locating sites with relevant data for the spcified years - very time consuming to locate

Metadata -eg. descriptions of the original model runs

missing data - I think weather stations must have closed but this was not easy to find out. Also, when you found a relevant station, with operating years, it was difficult to tell if the data you wanted was there before spending time downloading empty files.

More metadata regarding datasets (esp model runs) would help international users not familiar with UK syntax

Most of the times the accessing data is rectricted due to change of password or net difficulties

My attemptr to get data was basically frustrated by the burocracy.

n/a

Navigation down to appropriate files. having to go up and down 3 directories to change the flight I am collecting data from.

Navigation is often very slow on the website and I often use ftp. Some of the MSG data I wanted to use was an archive of "error" png files instead of the real data.

networking isn't quickly

Never keen to pay for something

nil

No

No big problems. Occasionally, in the early days, I would get lost in the website but no real issues now. no clear process to get data ,and nor clear link for data if you make a ftp link to download darta it will be easey

No problems

no problems

No problems - very fast response times, satisfied on this aspect

No problems at all. I really like the way the system works.

No problems.

No problems.

No trouble. There are some days missing ... most (or all?) are filled in later. (e.g. Nov 13,23 2009)

No weather data for 2004-2008

Non-academic requests had to be addressed to the Met Office directly, and the cost of obtaining the data was far too great for my own home use. Same data was available f.o.c. from

<http://re.jrc.ec.europa.eu/pvgis>

None

None

None

None

None

None

None

None so far.

None so far.

None.

None.

None.

Not always that obvious what the procedure is for accessing data, language can be a bit ambiguous. Wouldn't take much to correct this.

not at all

Not efficient HadRM3 PPE data extraction/subsetting system

Not satisfied with the discontinuity of European Synoptic Station data

not sure

On detachments, find that BADC availability unreliable over the weekend. In particular for uploading data and accessing websites held on BADC, but also for download sometimes.

Once I had figured out how to download the data it was then very easy to go back and download more or add data from other sites to my set. BADC changed the procedure, which again took time to explore and find again the right links to follow.

One of the dataset (flightline) could not be downloaded. Much later I guess I could download

Only problem is that the data is updated sporadically.

Passwords ...

Personally I wish MIDAS data was more easily available by station rather than by year but that is probably my own inadequacy in data handling. UK SURFACE DATA much easier to handle by individual station but only run to 2000, which is a bit frustrating. Generally though, this is a very helpful data base and I appreciate its availability very much.

problem of real analysis

problems that I have encountered are more to do with the data recording from the Met Office, rather than from the BADC.

Refer above

Replacement of old data series with new ones was not always obvious

see 26 a lot of unexplained jargon

Some data description ambiguities - specifically of date allocation of MIDAS TD daily maximums from 9am-9am reporting sites. Resolved by help desk.

Some data I got from the anonymous FTP can not be recognized by ENVI software.

some data was quite difficult to find as the data wasn't named as I expected it to be

Some issues accessing the ECMWF reanalysis products using the web based tool.

Some issues with access going out of date and unreliable web services, e.g. the ECMWF data extractor (an incredibly useful tool but which works around 50% of the time in my experience). Such issues are resolved very quickly when reported to the helpdesk. More warning of access going out of date and an easy way to renew it would be useful. More investment in a stable data extractor would be great for my research.

Some minor problems with accessing the trajectory model some times.

some of data cannot be unzipped and did not correct yet

Some software manual to access some new format data is not clear.

Sometimes it can be difficult getting the various scripts for plotting, etc which can also be downloaded or are given as links.

sometimes no data access may be due to technical problems

Sometimes the BADC data extractor stops working while downloading data.

sometimes the data we are looking for is not accessible to all BADC users. So signing, faxing and etc that takes time are needed.

sometimes the server seems to be overloaded

Sometimes there are problems with the data extraction tools which prevent data from being downloaded.

Still need to process the data to be compatible in GIS/RS

the people of non-England country can't access data

The 100MB file size limit in the data extractor makes the compiling of monthly files containing just one ECMWF data item quite laborious.

The 100MB limit on the BADC Data Extractor is absurdly small, particularly for accessing high-resolution model outputs (e.g., from the HiGEM and UJCC projects). There should be some facility for easily subsetting data from these projects without needing to download large fractions of the data. Currently, this would require many requests to the Data Extractor and a substantial amount of user interaction.

The change from pure text based to XML of the radiosonde data format played merry havoc with the

automated scripts set up for the processing of data,

The data I downloaded was, in the end, too sparse to be appropriate for my use

The data provided for the Midas stations had to be perused 'manually' to check for sites that had a full suite of measurements for the 1961-90 'reference' period recommended by the IPCC

the dataset link given should have properly mentioned what all parameters the data set is having before the user is downloading the file

The extractor is not all that reliable and can be extremely slow - I assume due to the amount of traffic, early morning is usually OK

The form of some old data is not so easy to read. But now there is not any problem.

The format of UKMO dump files has changed to pp format and makes it very difficult to re-create a dump file to run the UM on.

The GEBCO_08 Grid single file for the whole world is too large and prone to connectivity problems when discharged. It should be helpful if it could be splitted in several files to be reassembled by the user

The interface is very clunky when downloading different data items for the same time period.

the metadata for the Midas dataset could be both a) organised better, ie easier to find, and b) included in full on the same page as the data. Several times I have had to email to obtain full information about a particular variable, and this info could just be included with the data anyway.

The netcdf files did not seem to conform to specifications? Not sure, but I could not use software like GrADS to open them and had to use the files in alternative formats.

The online Data extractor can be quite problem prone. I believe it is being upgraded and hope this happens soon. There is a lot of data available that might be useful but many people will probably not persist, as it is not always clear before obtaining the data how relevant/useful it will be to the individual's specific purposes.

The only criticism I have is that it wasn't that obvious on where to find information of downloading multiple files (FTP). I did find it but took me a while!

The only problem I had was the length of time it takes to download the data. Would be useful to be able to download more than one year's file at once. The helpdesk service is excellent.

the only shortcoming for me is the speed with which new data are made available, and some missing data in sets

The server can be extremely slow when attempting to access data. This is true both for the FTP server and the BADC Data Extractor.

The server was down several times (sometimes lasting quite a long time) during the period when I was trying to access/obtain data.

The SHAC dataset I accessed was remote sensing data. The corresponding field data were not on NEODC. I found them elsewhere, but still they were incomplete and lacked explanation.

The size of the files obtained through the MIDAS database is too important. Is it possible to furnish one site per file ?

The tool to retrieve the ERA-40 data is not useful at all; see above comment

THE WEB DOCUMENT THAT ALLOWED ME TO ACCESS THE DATA WAS EXACTLY THE SAME AS THE ONE THAT ACTED AS THE PORTAL TO BADC ENQUIRIES IN THE FIRST INSTENCE, THUS I HAD BEEN ALLOWED ACCESS TO THE INFORMATION WITHOUT REALISING IT BECAUSE THERE WAS NOTHING TO INDICATE THAT I HAD BEEN GIVEN SUCH PERMISSION. CONSEQUENTLY A PERIOD OF ABOUT 4 WEEKS PASSED BETWEEN BEING ALLOWED ACCESS AND ACTUALLY REALISING THAT FACT. DOH!

The web interface is sometimes slow and is liable to crash or hang.

The website can be slow. I have had problems getting "missing data" which did exist "at source", but overall - a good service.

there are some miss data.

There are some problems with duplication of records within some Met Office datasets. These errors are random and the duplication is sometimes not complete making it impossible to use a simple computer program to edit the data. The errors may be with the original Met Office files or with the way in which BADC downloads the files from the Met Office

There are two main ways to access the main data set - either by files 1/data set/year (so you have to download and trawl through massive files to find observations from a few sites) OR through use of a data extractor which is quite clunky and very slow - it can take hours to run quite a simple query.

There is often problems when using the data extractor to obtain information

To use the weather files for the simulation program. Type of the weather files are in .dat or .txt. So,

need to convert into suitable type of weather file format.
took a long time to port the CRU TS3.0 dataset from CRU
trying to find datasets a little challenging
unable to find the data i am looking for without going round in circles, trying every possible option.
currently can't figure out why i can see file names, but can't download them (there's no actual link to the files themselves, and no message to tell me i dont have access).
Unavailability of data and the yellow key.
Very few relating to BADC, more the original data collection - however gaps I have come across have been sorted with remarkable speed and efficiency
wget did not for getting UKMO data when using ftp or sftp, could not ls directories (needed to use pftp or other software) - help desk was no help on this
Whenever we have had problems, the BADC was very helpful.
With the CRU 3.0 dataset I would have like the data to be available in more formats, for instance PCraster or GeoTiff.
yearly met station data results in huge files that need a specific programme to open them - it would be better if they were separated by src_id

Please provide any additional information concerning improvements or additions to BADC/NEODC data and services (e.g. list any data sets or value added services that you would like to be able to access but can't currently)

1 - We had to compute our own fields of EPV. It would be convenient to have EPV and potential temperature pre-computed. 2 - The format of the Stratospheric Assimilation changed after our need for the data temporarily stopped, so the availability of data readers (IDL, Python, etc.) will become important to us when we resume using the data.

A lot of data are currently classified as restricted which in other countries would be freely available. I think this can be improved.

A major advantage to holding several datasets in one place is that it should be easy to use them together. I don't know how easy it would be to implement, but if some form of recommendation could be made about related datasets also held when you access data from NEODC, that might be useful.

A radical improvement would be to make the data open access

Additional technical information on the sensors used to collect the data would be useful.

Aerosol data from the start of the satellite era Make data freely available WITH the tools such as Giovanni to process that data into useful information
algorithm to read the data

All Environment Agency rain gauge data

Anemometry data simultaneously taken at various heights would assist validating various models of the lower atmosphere.

As before, data in windows format (e.g. *.txt, *.xls, *.csv etc.)

As I said in response to an earlier question, all the national data holdings should be like the BADC

As on previous page It would be useful to be able to automatically inform all users who have downloaded a dataset that a new revision of that dataset is available

As stated previously re. stratospheric analyses, upward extension of heights, and greater time resolution would be welcome (though these are probably not under the control of BADC ?). At present my plate is full, so I don't have time to look around for other data sets of interest - but sometime I should do that.

BADC will mainly archive research council data without charge. Since we cannot hold all our data at BADC, we choose to hold all of our data elsewhere which makes BADC not very useful for us.

Better archiving of the original datasets used in climate research (i.e., not just derived products) is essential, but does not appear to be a priority.

better search facilities for locating data sets

Better version tracking (my reference here is CCMVal data access via ftp)

By indicating very high importance for improving the quality of the data held, and increase the extent to which processed data are available, I am referring to providing downscaled data. Such data would fill a vital gap in, for example, applying climate change data to exploration of adaptation and mitigation.

clearer guidance on downloading and specifying data sets from the uninitiated would be helpful
coastal wave height and frequency data

Continue datasets where possible

Could improve the data cleansing - e.g. so that you don't get repeated data. Also, I have to spend a lot of time collating data of different types from the same sites - it is recorded together originally, separated for storage and then has to be re-integrated. Why not store all daily data together, all hourly data together, etc?

DIGITAL [IE.SCANNED] GEOLOGIC SURVEY MAPS - 1:50000

Easier access to large volumes of data. Easier interoperability. Scope for harmonisation with NEODAAS?

ECMWF GEMS data - would be fantastic! I am really wanting to use this as part of my research but it is difficult to download due to only having a web interface and a file download limit. Also, GOSAT data would be useful, for the same reason.

ENVISAT-MIPAS, OZONESONDES, UTLS-ACTO...

Example: ECMWF Re-Analysis data; Met Office.

examples on how to download data to excel or cvs files

For my purposes it currently does all I need!

Getting easier access to global synoptic station data from individual stations would be helpful (currently I have to make a special request every time - which is always answered very quickly).

Give access to data for home users!

HadCM3, HadRM3

High resolution GCM data for initial and lateral boundary conditions to be used in RCM

Historical wind data

I didn't have any problems obtaining data

I have been finding difficult to get data related to wind, such as wind speed

I imagine that a lot of work goes on in biology and climate change and so some inclusion of bioclimate variables would be extremely useful (although perhaps that is just a personal thing)

I think NEODC should be aiming for something like: <http://calm.geo.berkeley.edu/ncalm/ddc.html> for LiDAR and possibly airphoto distribution. Priority should be given to making DEMs available as well as the raw data and then you'll find people use the data a lot more. This archive should be better publicised and made available to any researcher in the UK or abroad. Some people won't cite your data, but the vast majority will - and it looks so good for UK science to be supporting open and freely available datasets.

I think that one of the main difficulties is to find the right software applications to handle the data.

I think you can improve the list of data description in detail

I would like to be able to have hourly observations of wet bulb temperature or enthalpy of the ambient atmosphere at ground level.

I would like to see a more extensive set of UK air photos that would be ideal for me.

I'd like to access to meteorological data set. But I'm not a register user

Improve the speed and capacity of the web interface to facilitate faster download speeds.

In future, The BADC/NEODC can provide more kinds of atmospheric data.

Increase on the fact that it can be compatible with other softwares that are widely used.

It is great to have such a great dataset. however, only quality checked data could be held in the datasets. Currently there are many duplicates in the Ukmo-Midas dataset (both quality checked and unchecked values), and the clean up takes a lot of time.

It would be useful if BADC held all climate data so that it was not necessary to visit different websites (e.g. CRU) to get hold of different data sets.

Links to other national / international data services

Low-Level air data and upper air data and satellite data over West Africa with detail information

Met office MORECS data

More up-to-date global met station data More variety of EO data (including non-European sensors)
Most of the ones I checked as low importance are because they are already being done very well
Most of these improvements would require changes at FAAM not BADC for the datasets I use.
Much of the Nimrod rainfall data are in .dat files - these would be much easier to read if in standard image (gif or jpg) format The data extractor facility is very useful but is sometimes very slow
n.a.

n/a

Need to widen access to publically funded data e.g. Met Office data. Preferably provide access to public.

NEODC is very responsive to NCEO requests for data. We are satisfied with the service provided. If researchers ask NEODC for data the acquisition and access are efficient. We would like to see NEODC/BADC increase its role in climate change - this is happening to some extent but probably needs a more strategic approach, particularly to facilitate model/data intercomparisons.

NET RADIATION FROM SYNOPTIC STATIONS

No

no additional improvements

None

not at all

Offshore windspeeds would be interest

often large gaps in data or data have stopped being collected at useful locations (e.g. rainfall data at specific intervals)

on idea

Post processing the fields or taking out selected seasons or months of data would be helpful on the data server.

problems with metadata were really problems of CCMVal-2, not BADC

radar data

Raw weather station solar data

Real time high resolution ECMWF data (0.5 x 0.5 degree)

recent inshore, nearshore, terrestrial sediment core data/information. Seismic traces. Sediment texture/composition. Continual wave data - and data summaries (eg, annual wave intensity/directions)

References to papers that use your dataset would be useful

see earlier response

See previous note on terms and conditions

SEVIRI IR120 All sky Radiances

SHAC field data

Show some pictures and graphics of data and some global characteristics for example global sea ice area

Simplification of data format/structures for Midas temperature & precipitation data sets (rectangular data format compatible with statistical software, would be helpful)

solar radiation data

Some meteorological data for UK (temperature, rainfall et etc.) is available at MetOffice but not through BADC.

the availability of the data sets

The biggest improvement would be the availability of interactive data analysis/plotting as provided by eg NCEP Reanalysis Electronic Atlas

the updated CLAU data (up to 2008)

The WATCH forcing dataset would be handy.

to provide all miss data.

Trying to identify data sources (weather stations) that collect my required observation types was really very difficult.

UK Surface Data post-2000 by station

UM dump files from earlier periods

Unless there are experts in the field at the data centre improvement of data quality should NOT be done by the data centre but by the scientific community from which it came - and if necessary peer-reviewed - the data centre is a repository of science data and information NOT a place of which

undertakes science (this does not mean that it cannot be the host of virtual observatories or tools which process/analyse data on behalf of communities).

Up to know I am quite satisfied.

Use by non academic researchers and SMEs

very happy with the resource so far

Weather data for 2004-2008

Wind data between 0-50m from land or sea surface

Explanation of “yes” responses to “Do you create any ‘value-added products’ from the data you have accessed from BADC/NEODC?”

1). data from purpose built instrumentation coupled with provided data - gives indications on possible impacts of sea level rise at the coast. 2). Purchase instrumentation to augment web data sets, for example tidal attenuation.

after i am done the dataset for rhum and st kilda will have been completely reconstructed

After methodological assessments to specific legislative efforts of the European Commission

An additional quality control of the MetOffice-MIDAS data set was performed (Scotland-temperature and rainfall). Monthly time-series were created for 1961-2006 time period and 1890-2006 time period (this involved merging some records)

applied own algorithms to data held by the BADC

ARSF data processing

As part of my job, I generate high-level data products which are stored on the BADC.

ATSR reprocessing

because I have no data from BADC/NEODC

Bias-correction of model outputs

By combining a number of different datasets for comparative analysis

By data fusion with own data

Calculations producing integrated or higher order variables from existing data

CLAUS data has been combined with tropical cyclone data

Climate change Data for South Korea

collocated data set with satellite observation

Combining data into packages relevant to forestry

Computing additional atmospheric quantities from climatological data such as earth rotation parameters undisturbed from earth-atmosphere interactions.

Constructing local climate change scenarios using statistical downscaling techniques.

CWe are creating value added products elaborating long term time series of satellite data to automatically generate land cover change / land use maps.

Developing web-based services on top of the data.

downscale gridded datasets for comparison with obs stns and climate models

Downscaled GCM data for climate change impact studies

Downscaling of HadCM3 data for regional ecosystems modeling

elements of research papers

filling in 'holes' in pre-existing datasets

I am involved with the GRAPE project (retrieving aerosol and cloud products from the ATSR-2 and AATSR instruments).

I am running models of ecosystem services in Sheffield. The data I have accessed is used as an input to some of these models.

I and my colleagues operationally produce "derived meteorological products" from the Met Office Assimilation data for use with satellite datasets (currently NASA's Aura MLS and CSA's ACE); the MLS products are publicly available and the ACE products distributed by the ACE Science Team. The publicly available data (also for several no longer functioning satellite instruments) are distributed through the MLS website at JPL. Products/distribution are described by Manney et al (2007, JGR, 112, D24S50, doi:10.1029/2007JD008709).

I derive higher-order diagnostics to enter into my research.

I have combined one data set from the BADC with another from a secondary source since I use them in parallel regularly.

I have constructed a spatial database of MIDAS hourly land surface temperature for all United Kingdom surface observation stations from 1985 to present, removing erroneous and duplicate values. Database structure allows very fast and efficient querying of past observations and calculations on data. Spatially enabled database allows authorized users to connect and visualize the data within a Geographical Information System.

I have done some downscaling of the data.

I have produced algorithms that were given to public bodies for their perusal (civil protection, weather monitoring and forecasting). This was done entirely in a no profit way, as I am part of a government institution.

I have produced harmonised datasets for ease of use from the timeseries I download. They could be added to BADC

I have used the MIDAS and LINK HadRM3 data to produce agro-meteorological indicators of potential future agro-climatic conditions, which help strategic planning by land managers.

I hope so

I intend in future to submit long data sets of daily rainfall to BADC once these are compiled but have not done so yet.

I processed raw lidar data obtained from the NEODC to create filtered bare earth DTMs, hillshaded DTMs and DSMs.

I sometimes convert the wind data into hindcasts of wave climates

I use GIS techniques, a weather typing scheme and MIDAS met obs to create weather type climatologies for geographically similar sub-regions in Cumbria.

I use the raw data obtained from BADC to create visual displays of information.

I'm not sure what the question means, but I do write software that helps me to analyze the BADC data.

Improvement of simulation models

In the process of cleaning individual daily rainfall gauged records for the UK for long term trend analysis. I intend to share it when complete if possible, but have not yet.

In the sense that I use data stored from field campaigns in which I participate to run models to provide output.

I've combined Met Office wind data with modelled coastal wave fetch to produce indices of coastal wave exposure.

I've merged MIDAS and health data (I can't re-submit them to BADC because of confidentiality issues)

Mainly by converting data to more useful file formats

Meteorological data for forcing land surface models, which is based on atmospheric reanalysis but bias-corrected with observation-based data including CRU TS 3.0.

NCAVEO data set

New methodology within ArcMap and application of hydrological models

not in terms of weather products, but by using it combined with other data to analyse effectiveness of industry factors whilst controlling for the effects of weather.

not really sure what this means, but as the data enhance the value of other datasets and the conclusions that can be drawn for publications, then I guess this is the creation of a 'value-added product'

not sure exactly what is meant here though

Not sure if the GRAPE and GlobAerosol datasets counts here? Takes (A)ATSR level 1b to create level2/3 cloud and aerosol products.

Not sure what this means. We do weather-health research and publish it - a value added product?

Not yet.

Our project used weather observations in a model correlating health issues, creating value for health providers, academics and the public. The end result was a paper, which I suppose could be called a value-added product.

Outputs from models using BADC data as drivers

possibly in the future

PRODUCED A FILM DIRECTLY FROM THE DATA THAT DEMONSTRATES THE MOVEMENT OF SOLAR ENERGY THAT HAS BEEN ABSORBED IN THE OCEANS, THIS ALLOWS FOR THE LAY PERSON TO BETTER UNDERSTAND THE ISSUES INVOLVED. SPECIFICALLY SOLAR FORCING EVENTS IN WEST

AFRICA WILL EVENTUALLY IMPACT HERE.

Produced wind direction and speed statistics using Matlab for specific applications.

Projections of future river flows and water chemistry

Put for example, the data in Matlab matrix in order to handle them easily.

Research articles

Taken raw images of aerial photos and orthorectified/colour corrected them.

Tested methods presented in research papers using radiosonde data

The answer to the above is really "Not Yet" but the data could be used to specify model parameters for use in an energy industry tool to characterise the wind in wind generation simulations

The BADC data I accessed was for a specific purpose within a larger project (EUSeaMap) to produce predicted seabed habitat maps for large areas of Europe. These habitat maps will be made freely available via a webGIS as part of the EMODNET preparatory actions.

The 'merging' of datasets collected as part of project together to create a new common dataset.

The raw CLAU data has been processed based on filtering methods and the derived data has been used in research and teaching.

through simulations of models...

TMJs for energy simulations

trend evaluation

use of data in the context of a stochastic model

use of data to drive other models e.g. recent use of meteorological data to drive a dissolved organic carbon model for calibration against existing DOC data from the UK and then to use the model for climate change impact studies

used atmospheric fields for sophisticated analysis

used core data sets in conjunction with more specialist data to create calibrated merged datasets

used in consultancy

Used in verification of extended NAO-like circulation indexes. Ref. 34: these will be turned over to data center once validated and peer-reviewed.

Used to improve the performance of some of our models comparing actual met data with climate data.

Using BADC data has improved and enhanced our research

We do vortex edge and polar UVZT analyses and post movies on the web (if that is considered value-added - though I don't think anyone would pay for them) e.g.

<http://www.usask.ca/physics/isas/vtex90.gif> or <http://www.usask.ca/physics/isas/ukql90.gif> These are not linked from our site but we let other potentially interested parties know the access names.

Questions- 33-36: Now that you mention it - I do recall that there was some way of submitting results.

I haven't because I thought very few would be interested - and there may be some non-trivial description required to accompany visual displays. If I thought there was an interest, I would at least submit the links to the data (easiest - since we update the data on our site every few days), or the files. Usually - with good reason- the research attitude is "Not invented here" - because for publication you have to know *all* the details before the data can be used. We don't need extra funding to provide data products ... but it does take time - so we need to know that they are useful to others. To be useful, people must know they exist and what they are. Ease of access will depend on how and where they are "advertised". In a previous text window I have provided links to samples of our "products". More links could be provided.

We tried to provide a global, free service where downscaled climate scenarios would be available to everyone

We use HadISST SST to create an index of interannual variability in SST in the central Labrador Sea, in particular with respect to contributing to the ICES Reports on Ocean Climate.

We used a local version of the UM downloaded from BADC for the GSUM project. The GSUM project provided UM improvements to both the Met Office and the NERC supported version of the UM

We used the Met Office data to extract ozone and aerosol profiles from our data, and to interpret our ozone and aerosol profiles in terms of atmospheric phenomena. Our profile products are freely available to the public, and were used in published research.

writing my own codes to read the data which is time consuming

With colleagues, I have generated the 20th Century Reanalysis Dataset version 1 and now version 2.

The 20CR used HadISST accessed originally from BADC.

Please provide any other comments you would like to make regarding BADC/NEODC or the benefits of effective sharing and curation of data

"If BADC did not exist" is covered in the questionnaire but "if BADC ceased to exist" is not. If it were to be closed I think it would have a very serious impact on research as, I fear, many valuable data sets could be lost as the originating groups either do not hold copies, no longer exist or do not have the resources to support their own archives. The community has got used to BADC and come to rely on it - its loss could be crippling.

As I am a non-standard respondee, please feel free to ask questions.

As private citizen I always find the data interesting because I live near Chilbolton and I feel privileged to have access to it. But my contribution to your survey is actually irrelevant.

BADC - waste of time

BADC appears to me to have a culture of locked data sets and obscure formats - this does not promote data sharing - quite the opposite.

BADC could play more leadership in data archives from international programmes, because the BADC access systems seem to be superior to those of partners in other countries. In my view, what BADC does best is collecting the basic data in an archive which has a transparent structure. There isn't too much need for more complexity. Getting more data should be the priority. More archived satellite data would be good.

BADC data is available free for those in research institutions or universities, but other users must pay.

My use of BADC datasets would be increased if people like me, i.e. working as a consultant for clients such as organisations such as the Environment Agency and Natural England could use BADC data for free. I appreciate that it is desirable to recoup some data costs but the reality is that if the data are free then it will be used – if it is charged it is unlikely to be used. Also, there should be greater promotion of the available datasets to these organisations as I'm sure there are a lot of people who are not aware that the datasets exist, and so they are not used for projects that seek to make changes on the ground.

BADC has been a boon to Forest Research. Although we produce a lot of forest-related data sets, which would be of interest to certain sectors of the research community, we currently don't have an effective way of sharing that data - although we are working on that at the moment, we are still in the early stages.

BADC has been very useful in accessing good quality data for academic research in Universities.

BADC has greatly improved access to data for climate research in the UK. As noted there are some data errors in some files which may arise from the original Met Office datasets or may be a result of corruption during transfer from the Met office to BADC. Ensuring that there are no errors in downloading the files from the Met Office would be helpful.

BADC holds sea level data sets which I and others provided so in a way I am a service to them! I think the data holders pages could be more navigable.

BADC is a phenomenal resource for the academic community

BADC is very useful, and have provide a sharing database for academic research. Thanks.

BADC provide a useful, efficient and helpful service.

BADC should make their data set more usable

Being an oceanographer, my personal use of BADC has been limited. In my role as Science Coordinator for RAPID we have made heavy use of BADC and paid for the support that it has provided

Do not use because the NASA Giovanni system is FREE and so good it is not currently necessary. Any changes implemented to the BADC/NEODC systems should take the NASA Giovanni system as the very high standard you should try to emulate

Effective sharing and curation of data should be the priority in the agenda as the quantity of data is getting bigger and bigger. A platform like BADC is absolutely essential for research.

Effective sharing and curation of data, particularly for climate change research are vital.

NERC needs to look closely at its ambitions in this area and fund NEODC/BADC accordingly. Would be happy to discuss this further if you wish.

Email lists sometimes get hijacked by spambots selling medical supplies or similar.

FIX THE INTERFACE so it is easy to use. Again, I hold up the KNMI model,

<http://climexp.knmi.nl/start.cgi?someone@somewhere>

Generally great service; saves a lot of time. Thanks

Good data curation is vitally important; please continue to do a good job. I would like to see as much of the data as possible made available to one and all, without restrictions.

good work

Great thanks for your existence!

Have not provided any data for BADC but would be quite happy too if they were used. However, most of my project work is project based and therefore quite short term.

I am grateful for the opportunity to make use of summary meteorological data in analyses against Health data, sometimes to no ends.

I am grateful for the service and support I receive.

I AM HAVING DIFFICULTY EXPRESSING THE ENORMITY OF THE VALUE THAT SUCH DATABASES REPRESENT.

I appreciate the fact that this data are available. As an economist, this is not the primary type of data I use. But it has been useful to me.

I didn't know there was funding to provide data, how can this be accessed?

I expect to be able to supply value-added or new data products and would certainly provide them to BADC when they are proved useful.

I hope the workshop or training of using this data would be held. I would like to join. Thank you I is important to have a well-kept and organized data center. It makes search for data more efficient (many data at same place). Furthermore, the professionalism and continuity of a dedicated center (as opposed to "everyone on his own website" [for the time of the project]) is very valuable. Finally, only such a center can hold the large amounts of data arising from efforts like CMIP.

I know I should add data back to BADC but right now I don't own the other data, so it is not clear I could do that. I do fundamentally believe that open data policy is the most beneficial to the most people in the long run. I hope to contribute some day.

I tentatively answered that I will NOT provide my value-added products to BADC, but I do not mean refusal. It is just to mean that our project has not decided and that I cannot decide by myself on behalf of the project. Our project will make decision of data dissemination after we evaluate the product.

I think it does its job pretty well all things considered - perhaps suffers from lack of promotion?

I very much appreciate the accessibility of large environmental datasets and hope that BADC/NEODC will continue with their great work.

I was not given access to access BADC data despite my requests. I felt discriminated.....

I would like to state that the level of service provided by your colleagues on the HelpDesk is excellent, and the availability of this dataset for our research is of paramount importance.

I would not have been able to checkup the effects of climate on my study populations without access to BADC data and I think more publicity might help other workers to realize how useful these data can be.

In my opinion BADC are a world leading data centre and have world leading staff. I believe the question should be how to ensure this status is maintained.

In my opinion BADC is an essential part of science as a body.

In my role of promoting better data management practices with scientists I have used a lot of BADC information and policies as the basis for practice and advice within my organisation. The fact that BADC has already looked at a lot of key issues has been very helpful as have the BADC staff I have come into contact with.

In the academic community we are increasingly finding it difficult to pay for access to datasets: if we are working for the same government/organisation (NERC) through studentships or in preparing projects, I think it is ridiculous that these datasets are not openly and freely available for academic research.

In the past I have obtained meteorological data on the telephone. Now it is available in a more organised way it seems almost impossible to obtain at all.

it a great sharing

It is a fantastic resource and a credit to the bodies behind it.

It is probably worth ignoring these results as I have only had a username to BADC because of my heavy involvement in development / deployment of the user interface of UKCP09.

It is very useful for my research on climate change

IT would be good if the data were more readily available for teaching purposes. Perhaps a special interface for students to access a small subset of the data without too much administrative burden surrounding registration

It would be useful to access other datasets within a given geographical area without restriction. I've been delighted to use services provided by BADC/NEODC throughout my research. I hope to keep relationship to those services in the future.

Just, thank you!

keep it up. thank you

Kindly please send me the data that i had asked for.

let other coutry come in BADC/NEODC

Many thanks for a great service!

Many thanks for all your good work!

My experience in receiving permission to access the data and the download of the data was very easy, and I appreciate that..

no

No further comments

No more.

no other comments, thank you for the data access!

noaa

non

not at all

Original, hardcopy data needs to be maintained and available. Destroying original data severely undermines the ability to use climate data (or any other data) in a compelling manner.

Overall BADC is an essential facility that should be funded and supported at all cost.

Please be aware that, whilst I do have plans to use BADC data in my work soon, to date I have not *yet* been a significant user of BADC data. My connections with BADC to date are more to do with overseeing the access to climateprediction.net data by other people.

Please organise some workshops so that you ca teach people on how to access and effectively use this data. especially governmet policy makers.

Processing time to get permission to access new data set should be reduced.

real data is vital. To often data sets are to short (time). For example, to determine coastal changes long term data is required (hence collapse onto numerical models - eg wave hindcasting - which is not suitable for coastal dynamics, without the topographic data). Research funding administration helps create this ad hoc approach. Agencies that should/could fund research don't, namely the EA. Within organisations it is difficult to gain access, for example access to sediment textural analysis equipment, because of 'affiliation', not one of the team. Thank you for the opportunity Best

release data for research in Africa win more Funding from Africa oil companies.

see londonair.org.uk or airquality.co.uk for example of far more effective, navigable and intuitive access to air quality data is compared to the BADC data centre.

see my previous comments. I hope you will keep on like this. I am really glad that BADC is existing. For me it is quite helpful and saves me a lot of time. The only problem I encountered was with the UKMO data, but here I still have to check what went wrong.

Some questions only allow restrictive answers. Although to date I have not produced new data which might be of interest to BADC, if it revealed any significant findings it would automatically be offered to BADC.

some times BADC needs to be understand the financial situations for research students and grant the data on a free of cost

Sorry my feedback is probably not very useful but I hope I will be able to make use of BADC data in the future.

Sorry, can't spare any more time

Thank BADC, excellent!

Thank You

Thank you

Thank you for making the data available! I really appreciate your effort

Thank you ver ymuch for your service and efforts!

Thank you very much!

Thank you very much.

Thank You!

Thanks

Thanks for making the data available. It's a great service to provide original data online for academic research and humanitarian interests, particularly in view of the efforts of the last few years by some to take data private, and by others to politicise and control data. Hope you can keep up the good work!

thanks for your work.

The BADC has been an important part of my research over the last 8 years. Access to the observed weather data for the UK has allowed me to conduct several different areas of research which otherwise would have been expensive (buying data from the Met office) and probably more time consuming. The BADC is an essential resource and definitely falls in the category of indispensable to science in the UK

The benefits of effective sharing data Provides decision makers with better information to implement monitoring strategies

The data have made projects possible in a critical way. Without such data, such investigations would have been impossible,

The data which BADC/NEODC provided are very useful and convenient in daily research.

The NEODC is a fantastic data resource, with really helpful staff which is let down by availability, format and coherence of archive datasets. In addition, many of the older data were not recorded with reusability in mind, a fact that makes re-use of the archive for other purposes (ie archaeological prospection rather than landuse mapping for example). This can be, and is being, improved by better project briefs, but reusability of the data should be a key driver to ensure best value from the investment.

The newly produced 20th Century Reanalysis Project dataset version2 may be of interest to BADC. read about the dataset at http://www.esrl.noaa.gov/psd/data/20thC_Rean/

The survey was very orientated to accessing data from the data centre with very few questions on adding data. The latter represents some of the bigger issues for us.

These questions are already quite loaded towards BADC being a good service. Elements of it are, but I don't think the correct questions have been asked here. Also, I don't really see how we could answer some of these questions.

These services have enabled research to be undertaken that would otherwise have been impossible. Please keep up this excellent work.

This is a good service and helps a great deal with meteorological research. Such datasets should be made freely available for research purposes as this is how we can progress with our modelling efforts. to include analysis of the data dependences

To thanks BADC for providing the data.

Very good service

Very pleased with BADC

Very useful for our analysis of correlations in wind data leading to analysis of consistency of renewable power supply

We published 7-8 papers using UKMO data and always in acknowledgement the BADC has been thanked

Wider access of data that is publically funded e.g. Met Office data, should be set up - ideally such data should be publically available and certainly available to researchers who are based in NGOs.

With respect to 35. - I am asking for permission to give feedback on QC and other information that could improve the data I use.

Within NERC, BADC is one of the example of why scientists should maintain good data & metadata, and share them. Unlike some fields where datasets are of small size and can be owned and managed by a single scientist, environmental sciences rely on extensive datasets that can only be assembled and managed by a collective.

yes

You have done a good job.